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ESIRA — ENHANCING SOCIAL INNOVATION IN RURAL AREAS

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Authors: Jacopo Sforzi and Giulia Tallarini (EURICSE)

Contributors: Giulia Galera, Caterina De Benedictis, Silvia Scarafoni, Giovanni Saccon (EURICSE); Stefania Pedrotti (FTC); Giulia Candeloro, Luciana Mastrolonardo (BorghIn)

REGIONAL REPORT ON SOCIAL EXCLUSION AND SOCIAL ECONOMY INITIATIVES IN RURAL AREAS

Trentino & Abruzzo – Italy

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1. Introduction

This report presents the preliminary findings of the analysis conducted under T4.1 “Comparative study on social exclusion in rural areas” and T4.2 “Appraisal of existing policies, services and initiatives to support social inclusion and social economy in rural areas” of the ESIRA Horizon Europe project. This report will act as a basis of D4.1 “Benchmark study on social exclusion in rural areas” and D4.2 “Multi-level analysis of social economy initiatives in rural areas”.

Following a common methodological approach agreed upon with all ESIRA partners, the present report aims at:

1. Presenting an **overview of the Italian territorial system** and main information about social exclusion and inequalities in the country; main existing national policies to support local development and social inclusion in rural areas; conceptualisation and diffusion of social economy organisations and social enterprises.
2. Providing information specifically referring to the two selected Italian territories (i.e., the **Autonomous Province of Trento** - also known as **Trentino** - and **Abruzzo**), with a specific focus on the four identified MAPs: (i) the *Altavalsugana and Bernstol Valley Community* and (ii) the *Vallagarina Valley Community* (in the Autonomous Province of Trento); and (iii) the province of *L’Aquila*, and (iv) the province of *Chieti* (in Abruzzo).

In particular, the following topics are scrutinised:

- a. **Main characteristics of the territory**, in terms of its geographic situation, historical aspects, climatic and natural features, demography, economic situation, transport system and existing strategies fostering local development and social inclusion in rural areas,
- b. **Main groups of the population in the region at risk of/living in situations of social exclusion** and their characteristics, main drivers and indicators of vulnerability,
- c. **Main assets and potentials in the region**, with a specific focus on the role and contribution of social economy organisations in rural areas to reduce vulnerability and foster local development.

The report is structured as follows: **Section 2** presents the methodology adopted for the study. **Section 3** presents the country overview, detailing its territorial system, demographic trends, and various strategies and policies in place for rural areas and social inclusion, including insights into the history and evolution of the social economy and the Third sector in the country. **Sections 4-7** focus on the first selected territory, the Autonomous Province of Trento and its two previously mentioned Valley Communities. Following a regional overview (Section 4), Section 5 delves into the specific issue of vulnerability and social exclusion affecting different population groups within the region. Chapter 6 identifies strengths and opportunities in Trentino that can be leveraged for designing new strategies for the social and economic development of the region. Chapter 7 summarises the key findings of the regional analysis and explores potential directions and focuses for the MAP in the area. Mirror-like,

Sections 8-11 focus on the second territory (Abruzzo) and its two selected Provinces: L'Aquila and Chieti.

2. Methodology

The research methodology adopted for the analysis presented in this report included mixed tools: desk research, literature review, statistical data collection, and interviews.

For the **desk research and literature review**, both scientific and grey literature have been considered. Attention has also been paid to program-level documents and laws regarding the country as a whole and the two selected territories. Reports produced under the framework of other EU/national/regional projects have been considered as well.

This literature review was complemented with **statistical data** from central (mainly, the Italian National Institute of Statistics – ISTAT) and territorial (mainly, the Institute of Statistics of the Autonomous Province of Trento – ISPAT) statistical databases and from literature. Statistical data allowed – together with the other tools envisaged by the ESIRA methodology – to get an in-depth picture of the country and the selected areas, providing useful indicators (when available) to describe them.

Finally, in the period April 2024 – July 2024, we have conducted a total of **23 semi-structured in-depth interviews** with local (14 for Trentino; 5 for Abruzzo) and national (4) experts and stakeholders. To identify and recruit stakeholders to interview, all Italian partners work jointly, making the most of their respective knowledge of the territory and networks. Moreover, a snowball sampling technique has been adopted, as at the end of each interview people were asked to recommend at least (if possible) other 3 key informants. 19 interviews were carried out with only one interviewee, while 3 with two interviewees and 1 with four. Interviews were mainly conducted online and lasted an average of approximately 60 minutes. They were recorded¹ and then transcribed verbatim to facilitate the analysis.

A total of **29 stakeholders** were interviewed. Among them, 14 are women and 15 are men; 7 are from public organisations; 7 from social economy organisations and 9 from second-level organisations of the social economy. The list of respondents is provided in Annex 1.

No severe challenges have been encountered in the process of collecting literature and statistical data and in carrying out interviews. Nevertheless, some minor challenges may be identified:

- Literature and statistical data specifically referring to the four territories identified as MAPs were scarce. Often, when available, statistical data was outdated.
- The process of recruiting key informants to be interviewed has required constant efforts and time. A significant number of identified stakeholders did not answer/refused to be interviewed.

¹ Upon interviewee's permission.

- The identification of the territories for both MAPs in Trentino and in Abruzzo came alongside the drafting of this report so it was not possible to collect more detailed information (especially quantitative) of the selected territories.

3. Country overview: Italy

3.1 Territorial system of the country

Italy's territorial system is composed of **Regions, Provinces, Metropolitan Cities and Municipalities**. Regions constitute territorial bodies, while Provinces, Metropolitan Cities and Municipalities are local bodies. All of these four administrative levels are recognised as autonomous entities having their own statutes, roles, powers, functions and responsibilities in accordance with the principles of the Italian Constitution.

Regions are the first-level administrative divisions of the Italian Republic, and they are twenty, five of which are autonomous regions with special status: Aosta Valley, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Sardinia, Sicily and Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol. This autonomous status acknowledges their powers in relation to legislation, administration and finance, with a particular mention of the autonomous provinces of Trento and Bolzano/Bozen.

Regions have several legislative and administrative competences. In particular, they have responsibilities and functions with regards different subjects/fields: education (schools), health (hospitals), environment and protection of the territory, tourism and handcrafting. Moreover, regions shall establish their own taxes (in addition to State taxes) according to Italian law (art. 117 of the Constitution).

Provinces are the second-level administrative division, and they are an intermediate and autonomous level between a municipality and a Region. Italian provinces (with the exception of the current Sardinian provinces) correspond to the NUTS-3 regions. Totally, there are 80 ordinary provinces and 2 autonomous provinces (Trento and Bolzano/Bozen in Trentino-Alto Adige). Given their special status, they enjoy a high degree of self-governance and autonomy. The main areas of administrative responsibilities of provinces concern: defence and enhancement of the environment, cultural and artistic heritage; waste disposal, control of water discharges and air and sound emissions; provincial roads and inter-municipal transportation; and economic, tourism and cultural and sports promotion.

Italian territory counts other 14 institutional bodies of second level in Italy called “Metropolitan cities” (Bari, Bologna, Cagliari, Catania, Florence, Genoa, Messina, Milan, Naples, Palermo, Reggio Calabria, Rome, Turin and Venice)². They include 1,268 municipalities (16% of Italian municipalities) (ISTAT, 2023b).

Finally, Italy has 7,896 **municipalities**. As of 01/01/2024, the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT) reported 58,989,749 inhabitants, covering an area of 302,069.41 km² (density: 195 inhabitants/km²). The municipality is the third-level (and smallest) administrative division of the Italian legal system and has numerous functions and responsibilities, some of which are ‘institutional’, i.e. are assigned to the municipality by law and are mandatory for all municipalities (e.g., registry of births and

² *Metropolitan cities were established with Law 54, 7 April 2014, “Provisions on metropolitan cities, provinces, unions and mergers of municipalities” replacing the provinces.*

deaths and change of residence), while other tasks that fall within the remit of the municipalities are defined as 'socially useful': social assistance for people with disabilities (PWDs), the elderly and the poorest families; maintenance of roads and public green spaces; urban transport; construction and management of sports facilities; cultural initiatives and management of cultural venues (e.g., museums, theatres and libraries), etc. Some of these socially useful tasks are partly covered, from a financial point of view, by sums paid by citizens for the use of certain services (e.g., transport), by the tax on waste collection, and by other sources of revenues such as traffic police fines.

3.2 Distribution of Italian municipalities

70% of the municipalities (5,537) have less than 5 thousand inhabitants and, in total, 16.5% of the Italian population lives there. The medium-sized municipalities (2,355), i.e., between 5 thousand and 250 thousand inhabitants, represent 29.8% of the total Italian municipalities: 68.3% of the country's population resides in them. There are only 12 municipalities with more than 250 thousand inhabitants (0.2%) and 15.2% of residents in Italy live there.

The ISTAT classifies Italian municipalities on the basis of their altimetric threshold values into three main areas: **mountain, hill and plain areas**³. Most of the country's surface area is hilly (41.6%) and mountainous (35.2%). Even if the plain area represents only the 23.2% of the Italian surface, half of the population lives there. The 38.7% of the population lives in the hills and 12.1% lives in the mountains.

About a third of Italian municipalities are classified as mountain municipalities (Figure 1). 42% of the municipalities are classified as hills, while the remaining 26.6% as lowland. The Regions with an exclusively mountainous territory are Valle d'Aosta and **Trentino-Alto Adige** (in both Autonomous Provinces, including that of Trento). The regions with a predominantly mountainous territory are Liguria, **Abruzzo** and Molise.

³ According to ISTAT (2010, p. 4), mountain reaches a height of at least 600 metres in the Northern regions and at least 700 metres in the Central and Southern regions; hill does not exceed a height of 600 metres in the Northern regions, 700 metres in the Central and Southern regions; plain, low and flat, is characterised by the absence of masses.

Figure 1 Classification of Municipalities by altimetric zones

Source: ISTAT (2023b). Reference Year: 2022

Note: In dark and light red: mountain areas. In dark and light green: hill areas. In light yellow: plain areas.

3.3 Strategies and Policies for Rural Areas

a Rural Development Programme

Rural development in Italy is implemented through 22 Rural Development Programme (RDP) (one at the national level and 21 regional RDPs), which classify regions into three categories: “less developed”, “transition” and “more developed” regions. In addition, a national rural network programme supports activities of pooling and transferring of knowledge between the different actors of rural development in Italy.

Each RDP must aim to achieve at least four of the six European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) priorities:

- promote knowledge transfer and innovation in the agricultural and forestry sector and in rural areas
- enhance the profitability and competitiveness of all types of agriculture and promote innovative agricultural technologies and sustainable forest management
- promote the organization of the food supply chain, animal welfare and risk management in the agricultural sector
- encourage the efficient use of resources and the transition to a low-carbon and climate-resilient economy in the agri-food and forestry sectors
- preserve, restore and enhance ecosystems connected to agriculture and forests
- promote social inclusion, poverty reduction and economic development in rural areas.

Each Region, based on an in-depth analysis of their socioeconomic and environmental needs, define their own RDP.

Regarding the two areas identified for ESIRA, namely Trentino and Abruzzo:

- The **RDP of the Autonomous Province of Trento** (one of the two Provinces part of the Trentino-Alto Adige/South-Tyrol Region, Northern Italy, with the 97% of its area classified as rural areas with several complex development problems) put particular emphasis on actions related to restoring, preserving and enhancing ecosystems, improving the competitiveness of the farm and forestry sectors and promoting social inclusion and economic development in rural areas. Regarding this last action (social inclusion and local development in rural areas), more than 8% of the resources have been allocated to this priority, promoted through mainly technological and ITC activities and services, and through provision of basic services and village renewal in rural areas, including welfare and social care services. Local Development Strategies are implemented through a LEADER Local Action Group (LAG) approach which covers over 43% of the rural population.
- The **RDP of Abruzzo** (a Southern Region classified as "transition region") funded actions under all six Rural Development priorities, with a particular emphasis on preserving, restoring and enhancing the ecosystems related to agriculture and forestry as well as on improving the competitiveness of agriculture. Regarding social inclusion and local development in rural areas, the main actions of the RDP Abruzzo have been focused on the creation of basic services in rural areas (first of all, concerning ultra-broadband infrastructure, over €21 million will be allocated in order to cover 16% more of the rural population), support for local development strategies (LEADER), which includes the involvement of almost half of rural areas population, and the creation of about 50 additional jobs and farm and business development in order to favour employment in rural areas.

b National Rural Network

The **National Rural Network** supports rural development policies through the exchange of experiences and knowledge between rural areas, and through improved implementation and management of rural development programmes in Italy. The priorities are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 Main priorities, objectives and actions of the National Rural Network

Strategic priority	Objective	Actions
Improve the quality of implementation of rural development programs and promote implementation	- Improvement of the results and impacts of the Rural Development policy in Italy	- Support, analysis, research on rural development policies - Organization of exchanges of experiences and transfer of skills for planning and management of rural development - Design, implementation of information systems for rural development and support for evaluation and monitoring activities of the EAFRD and rural areas - Support for local development and integrated planning
Stimulate the participation of stakeholders in the	- Promote networking actions between companies operating in the primary	Connection, networking and networking

implementation of rural development	sector and between institutions, primary sector companies and other economic sectors	
	- Promote enterprise culture, access to financing and youth entrepreneurship	Services for rural operators
Information – communication on rural development policy and knowledge sharing	- Improve access to information and communication of rural development policy	Widespread dissemination of information and transfer of good communication practices
	- Active involvement of new subjects/actors in rural development policies	- Transfer of knowledge on rural development policies through an interactive approach based on collaboration between multiple subjects/systems - Creation of opportunities for discussion and involvement for active participation in the definition of rural development policies, also through integration with other policies.
Promote innovation	- Support the implementation of the EIP Operational Groups and connection with Horizon 2020 and national policies for research and innovation	Support for network activities for the PEI Operational Groups
	- Promote innovation in the primary and agri-food sectors and for businesses in rural areas	Services for the diffusion of innovation
Network management	- Ensure correct and effective management, communication, monitoring and evaluation of the National Rural Network Programme	- Activation, management and functioning of the Network structures - Network Communication Plan and publicity of interventions - Surveillance and evaluation of the Network

Source: own elaboration based on information reported in the NRN website:
<https://www.reterurale.it/en>

c LEADER

LEADER (*Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale*) is a local development approach used for twenty years to involve local actors in the development and implementation of strategies, in decision-making processes and in the allocation of resources for the development of their respective rural areas. In the 2014-2020 programming period, the LEADER method was extended to three other European funds, taking on the more general name of Community-Led Local Development (CLLD), a tool for involving citizens at local level in developing responses to the social, environmental and economic challenges we face today. LEADER operate through **Local Action Groups** (LAGs), which brings together both public and private local organizations from various sectors that operate in rural areas. LAGs develop their own local development strategies and manage their budgets, according to the different agreement that they have with their reference Region. In Italy, there are 200 LAGs⁴

⁴ In the autonomous province of Trento there are two LAGs, both established in the 2014-2020 programming period. In Abruzzo, there 8 LAGs established in different programming periods: 1 in 1991-93; 3 in 2000-06; 1 in 2007-13; 3 in 2014-20. Data are from the NRN website: <https://qeogal.crea.gov.it/default.asp?p=nazione&sp=1®ione=&qal=&i=1&cod=1.1.1-nazione>

While these previous national policies for rural areas are adopted by all EU countries, the following two national strategies have been created by the Italian Government.

d National Recovery and Resilience Plan

In 2021, the Italian Government launched its **National Recovery and Resilience Plan** (*NRRP – in Italian, Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza*). In Italy, the NRRP is divided into two main parts: one dedicated to main Reforms (e.g., Justice, Public Administration and bureaucratic simplification procedures); one made up of six Missions (Table 2) to pursue three main objectives:

- to repair the economic and social damage caused by the pandemic crisis;
- to tackle a number of weaknesses that have been weighing down on Italy's economy and society for decades (e.g., the long-standing divides between the country's geographical areas, gender inequality, weak productivity growth and a low rate of investment in human and physical capital);
- to go towards driving a comprehensive ecological transition.

Table 2 NRRP breakdown by Mission and by Component (EUR billion)

M1. DIGITALISATION, INNOVATION, COMPETITIVENESS, CULTURE AND TOURISM	NRRP (a)	React EU (b)	Complementary Fund (c)	Total (d)=(a)+(b)+(c)
M1C1- DIGITALISATION, INNOVATION AND SECURITY IN THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION	9.75	0.00	1.40	11,15
M1C2- DIGITALISATION, INNOVATION AND COMPETITIVENESS IN THE PRODUCTION SYSTEM	23.89	0.80	5.88	30,57
M1C3- TOURISM AND CULTURE 4.0	6.68	0.00	1.46	8.13
Total Mission 1	40.32	0.80	8.74	49.86
M2. GREEN REVOLUTION AND ECOLOGICAL TRANSITION	NRRP (a)	React EU (b)	Complementary Fund (c)	Total (d)=(a)+(b)+(c)
M2C1- CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE	5.27	0.50	1.20	6.97
M2C2- ENERGY TRANSITION AND SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY	23.78	0,18	1.40	25.36
M2C3- ENERGY EFFICIENCY AND RENOVATION OF BUILDINGS	15.36	0,32	6.56	22.24
M2C4- PROTECTION OF LAND AND WATER RESOURCES	15.06	0.31	0.00	15.37
Total Mission 2	59.47	1.31	9.16	69.94
M3. INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY	NRRP (a)	React EU (b)	Complementary Fund (c)	Total (d)=(a)+(b)+(c)
M3C1- HIGH SPEED RAIL/RAIL NETWORK CAPACITY AND ROAD SAFETY	24.77	0.00	3.20	27.97
M3C2- INTERMODALITY AND INTEGRATED LOGISTICS	0.63	0.00	2.86	3.49
Total Mission 3	25.40	0.00	6.06	31.46
M4. EDUCATION AND RESEARCH	NRRP (a)	React EU (b)	Complementary Fund (c)	Total (d)=(a)+(b)+(c)
M4C1- STRENGTHENING THE PROVISION OF EDUCATION SERVICES: FROM CRÈCHES TO UNIVERSITIES	19.44	1.45	0.00	20.89
M4C2- FROM RESEARCH TO BUSINESS	11.44	0.48	1.00	12.92
Total Mission 4	30.88	1.93	1.00	33.81
M5. INCLUSION AND COHESION	NRRP (a)	React EU (b)	Complementary Fund (c)	Total (d)=(a)+(b)+(c)
M5C1- EMPLOYMENT POLICIES	6.66	5.97	0.00	12,63
M5C2- SOCIAL INFRASTRUCTURE, HOUSEHOLDS, THE COMMUNITY AND THE THIRD SECTOR	11.17	1.28	0.34	12.79
M5C3- SPECIAL INTERVENTIONS FOR TERRITORIAL COHESION	1.98	0.00	2.43	4.41
Total Mission 5	19.81	7.25	2.77	29.83
M5. INCLUSION AND COHESION	NRRP (a)	React EU (b)	Complementary Fund (c)	Total (d)=(a)+(b)+(c)
M6C1- LOCAL NETWORKS, FACILITIES AND TELEMEDICINE FOR LOCAL HEALTHCARE	7.00	1.50	0.50	9.00
M6C2- INNOVATION, RESEARCH AND DIGITALISATION OF THE NATIONAL HEALTH SERVICE	8.63	0.21	2.39	11.23
Total Mission 6	15.63	1.71	2.89	20.23
TOTAL	191.50	13.00	30.62	235.12

Source: Governo.it, "NRRP: missions and components", <https://www.governo.it/en/approfondimento/nrrp-missions-and-components/19325>

Regarding the issues of social and work inclusion, the focus is clearly on **Mission 5. 'Cohesion and inclusion'**. However, other interesting aspects are also found within the other Missions, as can be seen from the following Table 3.

Table 3 Mission and relative Investment/Reform and Benefit dedicated to social and work inclusion

Mission	Investment (I.) / Reform (R.)	Benefit
M1C3 – Tourism and Culture 4.0 (6.68 billion euros)		
M1C3.1. Cultural heritage for the next generation	I. 1.2: Removing physical/cognitive barriers in museums, libraries and archives to enable greater access and participation in culture	Greater usability of cultural places for elderly, disabled and young people
M1C3.2. Regeneration of small cultural sites, cultural, religious & rural heritage	I. 2.1: Attractiveness of the villages	Rural development, increase in jobs, improvement in the quality of life of the inhabitants, fight against depopulation
	I. 2.2: Protection and enhancement of architecture and rural landscape	Rural development, improvement of the quality of life of the inhabitants, fight against depopulation
M5C1 – Employment policies (6.66 billion euros)		
M5C1.1. Active labor policies & employment support	R. 1.1. – Active labor and training policies	Work inclusion
	R. 1.2. – National plan to combat undeclared work	Work inclusion
	I. 1.1. – Strengthening of Employment Centers	Work inclusion, young people, NEET
	I. 1.2. – Creation of women's businesses	Work inclusion, women
	I. 1.3. – Gender equality certification system	Work inclusion, women
	I. 1.4. – Dual system	Work inclusion, young people, NEET
M5C1.2. Universal Civil Service	I. 2.1. – Universal Civil Service	Youth, NEET
M5C2 – Social infrastructures, families, communities and the Third Sector (11.22 billion euros)		
M5C2.1. Social services, disability & social marginality	I. 1.1. – Support for vulnerable people and prevention of the institutionalization of non-self-sufficient elderly people	Disadvantaged people, non-self-sufficient elderly people
	I. 1.2. – Independence paths for people with disabilities	Disadvantaged people, people with disabilities
	I. 1.3. – Temporary housing and post stations	Disadvantaged people, homeless people
	R. 1.1. – Framework law for disabilities	People with disabilities
	R. 1.2. – System of interventions in favor of non-self-sufficient elderly people	Non-self-sufficient elderly people
M5C2.2. Urban regeneration & social housing	I. 2.1. – Investments in urban regeneration projects, aimed at reducing situations of marginalization and social degradation	Contrast with situations of marginalization and social degradation, improvement of the quality of life
	I. 2.2. – Integrated Urban Plans	Support for vulnerable territories & for the suburbs, fighting situations of marginalization & social degradation, improvement of the quality of life
	I. 2.3. – Innovative quality of living program	Improved quality of life
M5C2.3. Sport & social inclusion	I. 3.1. – Sport and social inclusion	Social inclusion through sport
M5C3 – Special interventions for territorial cohesion (1.98 billion euros)		
	R. 1 – Strengthening of Special Economic Zones	Local socio-economic development (focus on the South)
	I. 1. – National strategy for internal areas	Rural development, support for internal areas
	I. 2. – Valorization of assets confiscated from the mafias	Fight against organized crime
	I. 3. – Structured socio-educational interventions to combat educational poverty in Southern Italy in support of the Third Sector	Fight against educational poverty, young people (focus on the South)
	I. 4. – Interventions for Special Economic Zones	Local socio-economic development (focus on the South)
M6C1 – Proximity networks, structures and telemedicine for local healthcare (7 billion euros)		

	R. 1 – Proximity networks, structures and telemedicine for local healthcare and national health, environment and climate network	Improvement of the quality of life, support for the population
	I. 1.1. – Community houses & taking charge of the person	Elderly people suffering from chronic disease
	I. 1.2. – Home as the first place of care and telemedicine	Elderly people who are not self-sufficient and/or suffer from chronic pathologies

Source: own elaboration based on information available on the Italian Government website: <https://www.governo.it/en/approfondimento/nrrp-objectives-and-structure/18999>

e National Village Plan

The **National Village Plan** (NVP – in Italian, Piano Borghi Italiani) is a program envisaged in the Italian NRPP aimed at supporting the economic and social development of disadvantaged areas based on the cultural regeneration of small towns and on the relaunch of tourism. The actions are structured around integrated local cultural-based projects. In particular, the NVP was made explicit through the so-called “Village Tender”, with the aim of hindering depopulation and promoting long-lasting, inclusive and sustainable economic development, full and productive employment and decent work. This instrument is part of the local development policies for rural areas aimed at rebalancing and strengthening economic, social and environmental relationships between urban, peri-urban and rural areas, supporting productive activities, new decent jobs, new entrepreneurship and innovation, taking advantage of local culture, traditions and knowledge.

The goal is the relaunch of **250 Italian villages** through **two lines of action**, as indicated in the following Table 4.

Table 4 The line of action of Village Tender

Line of action	Villages	Investments (€)	Description
Line A	21	420 million	Finances pilot regeneration projects identified by the autonomous Regions/Provinces (20 million allocated for each village)
Line B	229	380 million	Finances local cultural regeneration projects presented by the Municipalities in single or aggregate form (up to a maximum of 3 Municipalities) with a total resident population of up to 5,000 inhabitants (approximately 1.6 million euros allocated for each village)

Source: own elaboration based on the information of the National Village Plan website: <https://cultura.gov.it>

f National Strategy for Inner Areas

In the 2014-2020 programming period, within the framework of the "National Reform Plan", the Department of Development and Economic Cohesion of the Italian Government launched the **National Strategy for Inner Areas** (NSIA) in 2012. NSIA is an innovative public policy for development and territorial cohesion to tackle depopulation and marginalisation in Inner Areas throughout Italy. It represents an ambitious place-based centrally-driven policy (i) based on new multilevel local governance through integrated local promotion and development, (ii) aimed to promote and protect Inner Areas assets and local communities, responding to their needs and enhancing their environmental resources (water, high-quality agricultural products, forests, natural and human

landscapes) and cultural assets (archaeological assets, historic settlements, abbeys, small museums) and creating new social and economic opportunities.

The definition of Inner Areas – a classification of rural areas based on policy objectives – includes fragile territories, that and too often are abandoned to themselves, penalised by significant geographical (**low-accessibility**) and/or demographic (**low population**) and socio-economic problems (**low service and economic opportunity**) and far away (**remoteness**) from main centres as those municipalities that offer an exhaustive range of essential services (education, health and mobility)⁵. The areas have been selected according to the distance (travel time) from the nearest “essential services centre” (Table 5).

Table 5 The classification of NSIA areas

Classification of areas	Distance from services centres
Single – municipality service centre	-
Multi - municipality service centre	-
Belt areas	up to 20 minutes far from the centres
Inner Areas:	
‘Intermediate’ areas	from 20 to 40 minutes
‘Remote’ areas	from 40 to 75 minutes
‘Ultra – remote’ areas	over 75 minutes far

Source: National Strategy for Inner Areas, <https://www.agenziacoesione.gov.it>

Inner Areas stretch over 60% of the national surface, and host 52% of Italian municipalities and contain about 23% of its population.

NSIA is supported by European funds (ERDF, European Social Fund - ESF, and EAFRD), for co-financing of local development projects, and by national resources.

At the end of April 2017, **72 inner areas** across the national territory were selected as pilot areas through a public scrutiny procedure by all the central Administrations composing the National Committee for Inner Areas and by the relevant Regions and/or Autonomous Provinces. Those areas represent 1,066 municipalities, 2.1 million inhabitants, 3.5 % of the national population, 16.7% of the national territory.

The main goal of the NSIA is to promote new local development initiatives in the following fields:

- improving wealth and well-being of the population by providing (mainly through national policy) essential services (primary and secondary school, local mobility and transports, healthcare and medical services),
- land management and forests,
- local food products,

⁵ Essential service centres are those municipalities able to provide simultaneously: schools with a full range of secondary education, at least one emergency care hospital (with Emergency Room, general practice, general surgery, orthopaedics, traumatology, cardiology with intensive care unit, radiology and medical laboratory) and at least one “Silver” category railway station (from medium to small stations, which offers a medium-level service).

- renewable energy,
- natural and cultural heritage,
- traditional crafts and SMEs.

Local communities are essential in this process. Adopting a participatory approach to local development, the local strategy is elaborated through the cooperation between the municipalities involved in the project area. Municipalities have thus to work together in managing services for their communities, and also in designing and managing the strategy together with other local actors, like for instance LAGs. Indeed, there are relevant interplays between inner areas strategies and LAGs so much that in several places there is an overlapping (either totally or partially) between the two. Establishing synergies can be positive when LAGs directly participate in the design and implementation of the NSIA strategy, defining interventions specifically targeting the needs of territories included in the project area. In other cases, LAGs have a complementary role with respect to the inner area strategy, focusing on aspects not addressed by the latter.

Figure 2 Map of interplay between LAGs and Inner Areas

Source: ENRD, https://ec.europa.eu/enrd/sites/enrd/files/tg_smart-villages_case-study_it.pdf

Notes: in brown, overlapping between LAGs and NSIA strategies; in yellow, areas with GALs; in green, NSIA pilot areas. Lombardy, Basilicata, and Calabria: LEADER territories still not available. Campania: the municipalities of the last 4 selected LAGs are not available

Box 1 The National Union of Mountain Municipalities, Communities and Bodies (UNCCEM)

UNCCEM – the National Union of Mountain Municipalities, Communities and Bodies – is a national organization, present in each Region with individual delegations. It associates and represents partially or entirely mountain municipalities, mountain communities and unions of mountain municipalities. It also brings together various administrations and various bodies, including consortia, chambers of commerce, provinces, etc., which act in mountain areas. In total, UNCCEM represents a territorial basin equal to 54% of the national one and in which over 10 million inhabitants reside.

UNCCEM has the priority objective of promoting the development of mountain territories, through the promotion of a specific policy for mountain areas that includes mountain populations in the broader development process pursued at every institutional level, encouraging research and studies aimed at identifying solutions to be suggested to local authorities, the Regions, the Government, the Parliament and European bodies, as well as supporting and assisting local authorities in the administrative action developed in individual situations and in relationships with other public and private entities.

The main reference themes carried out by UNCCEM in recent periods are: (i) green communities for mountain areas; (ii) digitalization in mountain areas; (iii) shared administration processes in mountain areas.

3.4 Strategies and Policies for Social Inclusion

Several policies, instruments, and initiatives have been implemented at the national level to support the social inclusion of vulnerable people. These policies address **various targets** (e.g., young people and NEETs, women, the elderly, PWDs and migrants) and collectively aim to create a more inclusive society by addressing the diverse needs of vulnerable populations and promoting equal opportunities for all. Table 6 below lists a selection of the main national policies and initiatives.

Table 6 Main national policies and initiatives addressing social exclusion

Target	Policies and initiatives		
Youth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Universal Civil Service - SELFIEmployment - Integrated Plans for the Right to University Education - National Strategy for Digital Skills - I'm staying in the South 	<u>Focus on entrepreneurship</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Youth Guarantee - Guarantee Fund for SMEs - Tax breaks - Programs managed by Invitalia - Regional programs 	<u>Focus on NEETs</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Youth Guarantee - Local Work Plans - Active Policy Interventions - Social and Work Inclusion - Support for Return to Education
Women	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Law on Women's Quotas - Equality Plans at Work - Promotion of Gender Balance in Public Administration - Programs against Gender Violence 	<u>Focus on entrepreneurship</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Guarantee Fund for SMEs - Support for training and consultancy - Incubators and accelerators dedicated to women - Tax breaks (e.g. VAT exemption; Tax deductions for investments; Tax credits for hiring) - Competitions and awards for female entrepreneurship (e.g. <i>Donna Impresa</i> Award; Women's Business Award; PWN Milan Award) 	
Elderly people	<u>Focus on health, well-being & fighting socio-economic inequalities</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Old age pension 	<u>Focus on work</u>	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Purchasing Card - Social Housing - Social inclusion initiatives, access to services and active ageing (e.g. day centres; home and residential care services; continuous education and training; accessibility and mobility initiatives) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incentives for hiring seniors (e.g. Contribution relief, Solidarity Contracts) - Work-Life Balance - Pension Flexibility 	
People with disabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Law 68/1999 - Rules for the right to work of disabled people - Law 104/199 - Personalized Support Plans (PPS) - Fund for the Elimination of Architectural Barriers - Home Care Services 	<p><u>Focus on the role of the Third Sector</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Day centres and home care services - Training and work integration - Co-housing projects - Sports and recreational activities - Legal support and advocacy 	
Migrants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Immigration Legislation - Immigration System for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (SAI) - Extraordinary Reception Centres (CAS) - AMIF (Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund) - Economic & Social Integration Projects - Coordination of Integration Policies - Sponsorships & Employment Centres - Social cohesion projects 		

Given the richness and numerousness of these initiatives, for detailed information, please refer to Annex 1 where they are described comprehensively.

3.5 Territorial inequalities

In Italy, territorial inequalities have been an ongoing issue since the country's political unification in 1861. Specifically, there remains a significant divide between the North and South, with the Southern regions consistently lagging behind.

Although in 2023 the **gross disposable income per capita** of the total households increased by 4.2% (from EUR 25,505 in the previous year to EUR 26,576), the purchasing power decreased by 0.5% in the same period due to the rise in consumer prices by +5.9%. The analysis of the territorial distribution of the gross disposable income of households for 2022 (Figure 3) shows a still evident disparity between the North (EUR 24,350 of per capita income) and the South (EUR 16,062), with the Centre in an intermediate position (EUR 21,999). Only in Lombardy and in the autonomous province of Bolzano/Bozen does the income exceed EUR 25,000 per capita, while in Calabria it does not reach EUR 15,000.

Over the last ten years, in Italy, **nominal income** has increased on average by 20.3% and all the Southern regions, except for Abruzzo, have recorded a greater increase than the national average. Net income inequality is decreasing, reaching its lowest point (5.3) in the last fifteen years. In the South,

inequality is higher (5.4) than in the North (4.4) and the Centre (5.1): Calabria stands out with very high values (8.5) and Basilicata, where the disparity is more limited (3.6).

Figure 3 Gross disposable income per capita of consumer families, by region (2012 and 2022, EUR)

Source: ISTAT (2024)

Southern Italian regions lag behind the national average and **limited employment and business opportunities** continue to cause out-migration to other parts of Italy and demographic decline. This divide has been stressed also by most of the local stakeholders interviewed.

Interviewees underlined that the historical economic and social North-South gap has been further exacerbated by the consequences of the **Covid-19 pandemic**. Indeed, as shown by the latest Svimez Report (the Association for the Development of Industry in Southern Italy) of 2023, the increase in inflation has hit the weakest segments of the population, which are mainly concentrated in the Southern regions, hardest. As far as the labour market is concerned, the vulnerability of the Southern regions also remains at a critical level: almost four out of ten workers in this area have a fixed-term job (22.9% against 14% in the Centre-North of Italy). In addition, 23% of temporary workers in the South have been in temporary employment for at least five years (against the 8.4% in the Centre-North of Italy).

This vulnerability is even more alarming if one analyses the specific employment situation of certain categories of workers, particularly **women**: in the Southern regions, only about three out of ten women have a job.

The lack of job opportunities in the territory helps to explain – although it is certainly not the only factor at play – the **progressive depopulation trend** of Italy's inland areas, which is more acute in those of the South (-6.8% from 2011 to 2023) than in those of the Centre-North (-3.6% over the same period). This demographic decline is even more worrying if we consider two factors: firstly, the immigrant communities – although also present in the Southern regions – are mainly concentrated in the Northern regions and therefore their presence does not contribute significantly to population growth in Southern regions; secondly, that the depopulation of the South, which between 2022 and 2021 lost

1.1 million residents, is largely due to the migration of the under-35 population to Central-Northern Italy, thus exacerbating the phenomenon of population ageing in these areas. In fact, it is estimated that by 2080 there will be a loss of more than 8 million residents in southern Italy, which will become the oldest area in the country.

Moreover, Italian regions differ greatly in terms of demographic patterns, economic performance, well-being, and institutional quality and besides the classic North-South divide, a significant **urban and non-urban, peripheral, and rural areas divide** have been growing in Italy, resulting in uneven geographical development. This process has been accentuated by urbanization and industrialization processes that have unfolded in recent decades. In fact, many interviewees referred to rural areas, inner areas and mountain areas as fragile territories.

According to this overview and a study conducted by Fina, Heider and Prota (2021), the territorial inequality in Italy can be differentiated into four spatial types (Fina et al., 2021, p. 10):

1. *Regions of highest living standards with risk of social exclusion* (dark green in Figure 4) are home to a total of 11.8 million people (19.5% of the population) in 10 provinces (9.3% of all provinces),
2. *Dynamic city regions and affluent commuter belts of the North* (light green in Figure 4) are inhabited by a total of 20.1 million people (33.3% of the population) in 35 provinces (32.7% of all provinces),
3. *The solid centre and “bridge” between North and South* (ochre colour in Figure 4) are home to 9.8 million people (16.2% of the total population of 60.4 million inhabitants) and 31 provinces (29.0% of a total of 107 provinces),
4. *Disadvantaged regions with significant structural challenges* (violet colour in Figure 4) are populated by 18.7 million people (31.0% of the population) in 31 provinces (29.0% of all provinces).

The first “two Italies” have better performances than the national average; the third one, represents the average; and the last one has living conditions well below the average.

Figure 4 The Italian disparity map

Source: Fina et al. (2021)

Table 7 Bandwidth of indicator values for the spatial types

Indicator	Italy	Regions of highest living standards with risk of social exclusion	Dynamic city regions and affluent commuter belts of the North	The solid centre and 'bridge' between North and South	Disadvantaged regions with significant structural challenges
Unemployment Rate	10.4	6.7	6.1	7.4	10.3
Demographic dependency ratio	57.9	60.4	59.4	59.2	57.9
Share of employees in the high-tech sector	6.3	6.2	9.1	8.0	6.3
NEET - Share of working age people not in education, employment or training	22.2	17.1	15.9	17.8	22.1

Graduates with tertiary qualifications	25.7	33.3	29.1	28.1	25.8
Childcare services	13.6	26.8	18.0	16.7	13.7
Average gross income	11.0	11.6	11.7	11.3	11.0
Number of family doctors	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.9	0.9
Gender pay gap	92.1	91.0	90.8	91.4	92.1
House prices	1851.6	3080	2380	2077	1870
Voter turnout	74.0	76.5	77.4	77.2	74.1
Investment in social care	58.4	138	77	67	59.4
Internal migration balance	-2.4	11.5	7.4	3.6	-2.2
Broadband	65.1	70.9	59.0	59.3	65.0

Source: Fina et al. (2021)

3.6 The social economy and the Third Sector in Italy

Similarly to other EU countries, over the past two decades Italy has witnessed an extraordinary **increase in interest** in the diverse set of actors located between the public sector and that of for-profit enterprises. Not only economists, management scholars and sociologists, but also political scientists, historians, anthropologists and psychologists have studied this phenomenon, contributing to illustrating its determinants, potential, limitations and evolutionary dynamics from different disciplinary perspectives.

While the interest in this phenomenon is widespread and growing, the way of conceptualizing it is very different depending on the perspective adopted and the cultural traditions prevailing in the different countries. Indeed, the **scope of reference** changes if one wants to highlight exclusively those organisations that pursue general interest purposes, those structured as enterprises, or those that perform both an economic and political function (Galera and Chiomento, 2022).

As a result, the concepts that are being used to define actors other than public and for profit differ significantly across EU Member States (European Commission, 2020).

At the EU level there has conversely been a process of **progressive conceptual convergence** thanks to recent EU policy actions. In 2021, the European Commission launched the Social Economy Action Plan (SEAP) which sees the social economy as contributing to the development of the social dimension of the EU process implied in the European Pillar of Social Rights. While at the EU level the social economy has gained significant momentum, its degree of recognition varies substantially at Member State level.

The social economy has been recognised legal and/or at a policy level in those countries where there is a tradition of fruitful interaction between its components (associations, cooperatives and mutuals), such as in France, Belgium, Portugal and Spain (European Commission, 2020). On the contrary, it is **not commonly used as a concept in Italy**.

Based on the literature and recently delivered SEAP, the belonging organisations, namely: cooperatives, associations, foundations, mutual benefit societies and social enterprises, do not normally feel as being part of the same universe and to not share a common sense of identity in Italy.

At the same time, the social economy is rarely used as a conceptual framework by Italian researchers. As a result, the concept is little known by policy makers, at both national and local level.

Various reasons contribute to explaining the little success, visibility and recognition of the social economy among policy makers, practitioners and researchers.

Firstly, the **significant division historically existing between some components of the social economy**, particularly cooperatives, on the one hand, and associations and foundations on the other hand, with cooperatives looking at associations simply as voluntary entities, and associations blaming cooperatives for approximating traditional business organisations. In both cases, the specificities of the diverse entities covered by the social economy, particularly the red thread connecting them, tends to be largely ignored.

Secondly, the **widespread use of the concept of the Third Sector** also contributes to explaining the weak recognition of the social economy in Italy. The popularity of this other conceptual framework, which gained momentum back in the 90s, is mainly due to the effective promotional activity conducted by the National Third Sector Forum ETS (*Forum del Terzo Settore*). The National Third Sector Forum is the main body representing around 100 national organizations of second and third level which gather voluntary organisations, associations, social cooperatives, organisations working in the international development domain, as well as organisations dealing with ethical finance and fair trade. The Third Sector comprehends a wide spectrum of organizations ranging from small organizations to national networks, from social cooperatives to philanthropic bodies, which are given a common identity (Galera and Chiomento, 2022). And which, together, reflect the richness of an important component of Italy's country's organized civil society and its ability to develop innovative responses and unprecedented solutions to increasingly fluid and complex challenges and needs.

The relevance of the Third Sector was moreover strengthened by its legal recognition in 2016 with the adoption of **Law 106/2016**, which clearly defines the boundaries and operating rules of the Third Sector. Under the Third Sector, the Italian legislator aggregated and regulated exclusively organisations “pursuing the general interest”. This way, it excluded those organisations, such as cooperatives and mutual benefit organisations, that pursue purely mutual objectives, unless they acquire the status of social enterprise, thereby adopting objectives, restrictions on profit distribution and governance models consistent with the definition of the Third sector (see **Legislative Decree No 117/2017** – Third Sector Code, and Legislative Decree No 112/2017 on social enterprise).

By excluding entrepreneurial non-profit organisations that pursue a mutual purpose, such as traditional cooperatives, the legal recognition of the Third Sector has crystallised the division between cooperatives and welfare associations even further, continuing - however - to implicitly look at **social cooperatives as a sort of bridging element** which connects the world of cooperatives with that of traditional welfare associations.

The Italian Third Sector has its roots in the **Catholic tradition** and in the **social movements** (Ianes & Borzaga, 2021; Borzaga & Ianes, 2006; Gori, 2022), including charitable entities and congregations which, starting from the early Middle Ages, in the absence of a public system of assistance for people in need, struggled to tackle the needs of the most impoverished groups of the population.

The freedom of action, self-organization and self-reliance of civil society suffered a severe setback with the entry into force of Law no. 6972 of 1890 (so called “Crispi Law”), which transformed the *Opere Pie* from private institutions into **Public Assistance and Charity Institutes (IPAB)**. The advent of the **fascist regime** did the rest, attracting a large part of the welfare sphere and instrumentalising what remained of organized civil society for political purposes and collective control.

A phase of marginalization of the Third Sector begun, which continued with the nascent welfare state, which took shape after the Second World War. Indeed, unlike other European countries, in Italy civil society organizations were entrusted with a sole **advocacy role**, while the delivery of services - which for over a century had made it possible to respond to a set of unmet needs - was actually forbidden.

It is therefore no coincidence that in one of the first international studies on the sector - then commonly defined as the “voluntary sector” - published in 1991, Ted Perlmutter argued that the Italian Third Sector was almost non-existent, or at least invisible and forecasted its irrelevant role for the years to come (Perlmutter, 1991).

Perlmutter’s prediction has of course been proved incorrect due to the dramatic increase in number of two types of entities: social cooperatives and voluntary organisations. The first social cooperatives emerged at the **end of the 1970s**, in the same period that witnessed the flourishing of organized volunteer groups. Such initiatives were mainly started by groups of volunteers who were dissatisfied with the poor provision of public social and community care services.

Starting from the end of the last century, in a couple of years the Third Sector filled the void left by a poor, backward and seriously flawed welfare system both in terms of insurance coverage and above all in terms of the supply of services. And it did so in a very dynamic way: developing from below, experimenting with new organizational forms and designing innovative services, which have contributed to transforming the welfare system in a profound way. This evolution was accompanied by various legal recognitions of a number of organizational forms, including **social promotion associations (Law no. 383 of 2000)** and **social enterprises (as social cooperatives by means of Law no. 381/1991 and Law 118 of 2005 and Legislative Decree no. 155 of 2006)**.

In the meantime, there has been a stable increase, even in times of economic crisis, both in the number of operating organizations and in the number of staff employed. According to the latest ISTAT Census, in 2020, **363 498 Third Sector organizations** were operating (compared to 301 191 in 2011) with **870 183 employees** (compared to 680 811 in 2011) supported by more than 5 million volunteers.

Following this evolution, from being a marginal player in the Italian economic and welfare system, the Third Sector has progressively gained social, employment and economic relevance. Thanks to the legal recognition of individual components, the Third Sector has gradually developed into a **structured landscape**; alongside a rich associative sector and a diversified world of volunteering, especially noteworthy is the contribution of social cooperatives.

3.7 Social enterprises

Another concept which is widely used in Italy is the *social enterprise*, which was actually used for the first time in Italy in the **1980s** to identify the innovative private initiatives established by volunteer groups that had been developed to deliver social services or provide economic activities designed to facilitate the integration of disadvantaged people (Ianes and Borzaga, 2021). Since the 1990s, the diffusion of social enterprises has been linked to the introduction of **Law 381 of 1991**, which actually acknowledged social cooperatives ex post, after they had been developing empirically from below over more or less a decade thanks to the mobilisation of civil society. It was the first law of this kind to be adopted, which was subsequently regarded as a **reference point by other countries** that followed a similar route, such as France, South Korea, Portugal, and Poland.

The main characteristics of the Italian law on social cooperatives are the definition of a **general-interest goal** that social cooperatives are expected to pursue, including the focus on the types of services⁶; the assignment of both **collective ownership and democratic governance** according to open-door and one-person, one-vote cooperative principles; the possibility of engaging a **plurality of stakeholders** (including remunerated workers, beneficiaries, and volunteers); and the imposition of severe **constraints on the distribution of profits** (Galera & Borzaga, 2009).

The first social enterprise initiatives emerged at the end of the **1970s**, in the same period that witnessed the flourishing of organized volunteer groups. Such initiatives were mainly started by groups of volunteers who were dissatisfied with the poor provision of public social and community care services.

Most of these initiatives were initially organized as associations. Since the 1980s, however, the use of the cooperative form has rapidly become widespread. These cooperatives provided **social services** to meet the needs of groups of people not served by public policies (e.g., PWDs, drug addicts and youth with social problems, homeless people). They promoted activities that aimed to integrate disadvantaged people into work. However, from the very beginning, the new cooperatives differed from traditional ones because of the goals pursued. They did not aim to promote the interests of their members; rather, they aimed to provide **solidarity to people in need** who had been neglected by public policies. Unlike traditional cooperative forms, the new cooperatives included **volunteers** in their membership. In 1981, both voluntary organizations and social solidarity cooperatives began raising requests for legal acknowledgement (Borzaga & Galera, 2023; Borzaga & Galera, 2016). In 1991, this acknowledgement was accomplished following the approval of two distinct laws: the Act on Voluntary Organizations (no. 266) and the Act on Social Cooperatives (no. 381).

Next, the law conceives social cooperatives as **collective organizations**, which are encouraged to involve the local community and represent the interests of different classes of stakeholders. The law also allows for the simultaneous involvement of different categories of members in the ownership

⁶ With a distinction between social cooperatives providing social assistance, health and educational services and those that aim to integrate disadvantaged people to work.

structure, including workers, users, volunteers, financing members. In addition to individuals also legal entities can join as members (Borzaga & Galera, 2016).

Finally, social cooperatives must comply with a **non-profit distribution constraint**. This means they are allowed to achieve profits, but a consistent part of such profits must be accumulated by law into locked assets. Moreover, the law foresees the indivisibility of assets, which means that members are not allowed to privately appropriate assets generated by the entrepreneurial activity.

The enactment of Law 381 led to the extraordinary growth of social cooperatives. Since 1991, social cooperatives have been registering a 10% to 20% average annual growth rate. They nearly doubled in number from a little over 2,000 before regulation to 3,900 in 1996 and reached 7,363 in 2005 (ISTAT, 2007). In 2011, there were 12 264 social cooperatives employing a total of 365 006 workers, of which 30 534 were disadvantaged. These social cooperatives supplied about 50% of all welfare services. Each cooperative had an average of 32.41 employees, implying that 613 out of 100 000 inhabitants in Italy were employed in social cooperatives. Other than ordinary workers, social cooperatives also employ a large number of volunteers, amounting to 42 000 in 2011 (ISTAT, 2011). Social cooperatives have continued to grow during the years of the financial crisis, reaching 13 000 at the end of 2013, with a turnover of more than 10 billion euros, 2 billion in locked assets, over 390 000 employees (mostly members) and between 6 and 8 million users (Borzaga & Galera, 2016). According to the latest ISTAT census on non-profit organisations, in 2020 there were **14 984 social cooperatives**, and they employed **461 468 workers**. Compared to the 2011 Census, the growth rate was 44%. Although representing only 4.1% of the total non-profit organisations, they employed 52.9% of the workers. Of these, approximately one third (5 200) were work integration cooperatives, a percentage that has remained virtually unchanged since the end of the 1990s (Borzaga & Galera, 2016).

The Italian debate on social enterprise did not end with the entry into force of Law 381. In particular, the debate highlighted **three limits of Law 381** and of the regulatory context in which these organizations operated, i.e. the Civil Code.

The first concerns the sectors of activity envisaged by Law 381, which began to appear too narrow compared to the wealth of experiences that were developing in areas of general interest other than social-welfare, educational and job placement, such as, for example, culture, healthcare, tourism for people with disabilities and disadvantaged people, training and protection of the environment and landscape. The second concerns the need to regulate the various forms of associations and foundations that operate as social enterprises without assuming the status of an enterprise. The third is related to the need to recognize and regulate also all those subjects, such as religious bodies, carrying out economic activities with social purposes, albeit in a non-cooperative manner (Borzaga & Galera, 2023).

The debate paved the way to the approval of Law 118 in 2005 and in the following year of Decree-law 115. The new decree introduces the qualification of social enterprise which can be assumed by all the legal forms that are regulated by the Civil Code, provided that they comply with certain structural and organizational requirements. The law requires associations and foundations to structure themselves in order to carry out economic activities in a stable and continuous manner, while limited liability

companies, joint-stock companies and cooperatives other than social ones must observe the restriction on the distribution of profits.

Table 8 summarises the main representative actors of the social economy at the national level. For further details, please refer to Annex 2.

Table 8 Main representative actors of the social economy at the national level

Cooperative Movement	Confcooperative
	Legacoop
	General association of Italian cooperatives (Agci)
	Consorzio Gino Mattarelli (CGM)
Third sector	CSVnet
	Caritas
	National Third Sector Forum
	Community Foundations

4. Regional overview: Trentino

4.1 The main characteristics of the territory

As already mentioned, the Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol region is unique because it is divided into two autonomous Provinces, each with significant legislative and administrative autonomy.

Figure 5 Map of Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol Region

Here is an overview of Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol administrative structure:

a. **Regional Level:** Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol

Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol is one of Italy's five autonomous regions, recognised for its special status that grants it greater legislative and administrative powers compared to ordinary regions. The region has its own regional council (*Consiglio Regionale*) and regional government (*Giunta Regionale*). However, due to the high level of autonomy granted to the two provinces, the regional level has relatively limited powers and has mainly a coordination function for the two provinces.

b. **Provincial Level:** Two Autonomous Provinces, i.e. Province of Trento (*Provincia Autonoma di Trento*)⁷ and Province of Bolzano/Bozen (*Provincia Autonoma di Bolzano/Autonome Provinz Bozen – Südtirol*).

c. **Municipal Level:** Both autonomous provinces are subdivided into municipalities (*Comuni*), which are the smallest administrative units. These municipalities are responsible for local governance and public services.

⁷ Throughout the report, the terms “Autonomous Province of Trento” and “Trentino” are used interchangeably.

Table 9 below specifies the main characteristics of the two provinces.

Table 9 Trentino provincial level: main characteristics

	Province of Trento	Province of Bolzano/Bozen
Capital	Trento	Bolzano
Official languages	Italian	German, Italian, and Ladin
Governance	Provincial council (<i>Consiglio Provinciale</i>) responsible for legislative functions and provincial government (<i>Giunta Provinciale</i>), which handles executive duties	Provincial council (<i>Consiglio Provinciale</i>) responsible for legislative functions and provincial government (<i>Giunta Provinciale</i>), which handles executive duties
Municipalities	166	116

As it independently manages many of the competencies normally reserved for the central State (such as those in the areas of education, culture, health, roads, transport, and tourism) in 2006 the Autonomous Province of Trento established the **Valley Communities** (*Comunità di Valle*), i.e., local territorial bodies that form the intermediate institutional level between the municipalities and the Province (see Figure 6). These 16 entities are formed by an associative structure, compulsorily made up of the municipalities included in each territory. They are entitled to exercise important administrative functions, e.g. related to territorial and urban planning, social services and health, education, economic and tourism development, infrastructure, and culture and sport.

Figure 6 Valley Communities in the Autonomous Province of Trento

From an historical perspective, the special institutional set-up of the Autonomous Province of Trento is deeply rooted in its historical background: before World War I, the Trentino area was part of the

Austro-Hungarian Empire⁸. The region had a distinctive cultural and administrative identity within the empire. After the war, in 1919, the region became part of Italy under the Treaty of Saint-Germain-en-Laye. The transition created tensions due to the different administrative and cultural traditions. In response to these tensions, particularly in South Tyrol, Italy granted significant autonomy to the Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol region through the **1948 Autonomy Statute**. The aim was to protect the German-speaking minority in South Tyrol and address the unique needs of the Trentino area. The **second Autonomy Statute (1972)** further enhanced the powers of the provinces of Trento and Bolzano. This arrangement effectively divided the region’s autonomy between the two provinces, recognizing their distinct identities.

With the advent of the **European Union** and the cross-border cooperation initiatives, Trentino has benefitted from enhanced regional cooperation, particularly with neighbouring Austrian regions.

Thus, the **unique institutional set-up** enjoyed by the Autonomous Province of Trento reflects its historical, cultural, and geographical specificities. The province administers its budget, manages natural resources, and oversees cultural and linguistic matters, reflecting the local needs and preferences. Moreover, it has its own tax system and retains a substantial portion of the taxes collected within the province, ensuring financial self-sufficiency. Lastly, the autonomy arrangement allows the Autonomous Province of Trento to maintain and promote its local cultural, linguistic, and historical identity while ensuring effective local governance.

4.2 Geographic and historical aspects

Trentino covers an area of more than **6,000 km²** and it is an alpine, mainly **rural region**, with the majority of municipalities classified as small (500– 1,000 inhabitants). The main urban centres in the area are Trento (120,000 inhabitants) and Rovereto (40,000 inhabitants).

Figure 7 Map of the Autonomous Province of Trento⁹

⁸ For more details about the history of the region, see Section 4.3 “Historical aspects”.

⁹ Author: Idéfix at nl.wikipedia, CC BY-SA 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=3218742>

More than 70% of the territory is located above 1,000 masl and about 67% of it is covered by forest and other wooded land. The eastern part of Trentino is dominated by the Dolomites, a UNESCO World Heritage Site known for its limestone formations, sheer cliffs, and distinctive pale colour¹⁰. The entire territory is classified as a **mountainous disadvantaged area** under the European Economic Community Directive no. 268 of 1975 and by the Italian Legislative Decree no. 146 of 1997.

Adige Valley (*Val d'Adige*) is the primary valley running through the Province, formed by the Adige River, the second longest river in Italy. The valley is crucial for agriculture, particularly vineyards and apple orchards, and hosts key transport routes including the A22 motorway. Val di Fassa, Val di Fiemme, Val di Non, and Val Rendena are known for their scenic beauty, agriculture, and tourism, particularly for winter sports and hiking.

The northern tip of **Lake Garda**, Italy's largest lake, lies within Trentino. The lake is a major tourist destination. Popular for sailing, windsurfing, and other water sports, as well as surrounding hiking and biking trails. Lake Levico, lake Caldonazzo, and lake Molveno are smaller alpine lakes known for their pristine waters and are popular destinations for tourists.

Trentino is characterized by **cold winters** with significant snowfall, particularly in the higher altitudes. In the valleys, **summers are warm** and can be humid, while winters are cold but less severe than in the higher regions.

Trentino boasts rich **biodiversity**, with extensive forests covering much of the Province¹¹ and a variety of wildlife, including brown bears, ibex, chamois and eagles. The Autonomous Province of Trento is home to several protected areas, including three national parks¹².

Historically, Trentino has long been a crossroads of civilizations, each leaving its mark. Human presence dates back to the **Paleolithic era**. Under **Roman rule**, Trentino thrived as a key trade and military hub, with Tridentum (modern Trento) benefiting from the Via Claudia Augusta and advanced infrastructure.

After the fall of the Western Roman Empire in the 5th century, Trentino transitioned through **Ostrogothic, Lombard, and Carolingian rule**, with feudalism and powerful bishoprics shaping the medieval era. Trento grew into a cultural and economic centre during the **Renaissance**.

The **Habsburgs' rule** from the 16th century brought stability and reforms, but 19th-century **nationalist movements** saw Italian-speaking Trentino striving for unification with Italy. Despite remaining under Austrian control after the Third Italian War of Independence (1866), Trentino joined Italy following **World War I** and the **Treaty of Saint-Germain** (1919).

The **interwar period** posed challenges, including tensions with South Tyrol's German-speaking population under fascism. After **World War II**, Trentino – together with South Tyrol - gained

¹⁰ Notable peaks include the Pale di San Martino and the Marmolada, which is the highest peak in the Dolomites at 3 343 meters. The western part of the province includes parts of the Southern Limestone Alps, particularly the Adamello-Presanella group and the Ortler Alps. Important peaks in these ranges include Cima Presanella and the Adamello.

¹¹ These forests include coniferous trees like spruces and larches, and broadleaf trees like beeches and chestnuts.

¹² Stelvio National Park (*Parco Nazionale dello Stelvio*), Paneveggio-Pale di San Martino Nature Park (*Parco Naturale Paneveggio-Pale di San Martino*) and Adamello Brenta Nature Park (*Parco Naturale Adamello Brenta*).

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autonomous status within the **Italian Republic** (established in 1946), which recognises its unique cultural and linguistic heritage. This autonomy facilitated economic development and fostered a spirit of cooperation and coexistence between the region's diverse communities.

4.3 Demography

As of 01/01/2023, Trentino has a **total population of 542,996** (ISPAT, 2024a).

Inner migration trends show a **positive migration balance**, with more people moving into the region than leaving. This influx is partly driven by Trentino's high quality of life, economic opportunities, and scenic landscapes. However, despite the positive migration balance, the overall total population change is modest, reflecting the broader demographic trend of **low birth rates** (ISPAT, 2024a).

The region faces challenges related to **ageing and depopulation**, especially in rural and mountainous areas. Indeed, the child population share (under 18) constitutes about 16% of the total population, reflecting a relatively young demographic segment but the old age population share (65 and older) accounts for roughly 23%, indicating a significant ageing population (ISPAT, 2023a).

The ageing population poses **significant social and economic challenges**, including increased demand for healthcare services and a shrinking workforce. Depopulation in certain areas also threatens the sustainability of local communities. Efforts to address these issues include policies aimed at supporting families, encouraging births, and attracting young professionals to the region. These measures aim to balance the demographic scales and ensure sustainable development for Trentino's future.

4.4 Economic situation

Trentino boasts a **robust and dynamic economy**. As of the latest available data, the region's GDP (over EUR 23 billion) per capita stands at approximately EUR 43,000 (+30% compared to the national average of EUR 33,000), reflecting its strong economic performance relative to other Italian regions (ISPAT, 2023b).

Trentino's economy is diverse, with key sectors including **agriculture, tourism, manufacturing, and services**. The Adige Valley is particularly fertile, supporting extensive vineyards and orchards. Apples and wine production are significant. Tourism is a major economic driver, particularly for skiing in winter, hiking, and mountaineering in summer. Cultural tourism is also important, with historic sites and events. There are also industrial activities, particularly in the production of machinery, food products, and textiles.

The **employment rate** is notably high, reaching around 70% within the age group 15-64 in the first quarter of 2024 (61.7% higher than the national average)¹³. This figure highlights the region's effective labour market and the availability of job opportunities across various industries.

¹³ Data from ISTAT (2024) *Lavoro e retribuzioni*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

The Autonomous Province is home to a vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem, with **cooperative enterprises** that constitute a significant portion of the regional economy and play a significant role in the area, both economically and socially. Indeed, cooperatives in Trentino make a substantial contribution to the region's GDP, particularly in the agricultural and financial sectors, and a significant proportion of the population is involved in cooperatives, either as members, employees, or beneficiaries of cooperative services. Indeed, Trentino has a long history of **cooperative movements**, which have been instrumental in fostering local development, social inclusion, and economic resilience and is a remarkable example of community-driven economic development (Salvatori, 2011).

Overall, Trentino's economic landscape is characterized by **stability, growth, and inclusivity**, making it an attractive region for both investment and living. The continued focus on sustainable development and social cohesion ensures a positive outlook for the region's future.

4.5 Institutional setting

The province is **well-connected by road and rail**. The A22 motorway is a crucial North-South route connecting Italy with Austria. Public transport within the province includes a network of buses and regional trains.

Despite the robust infrastructure, Trentino faces several **transport-related challenges**. One significant issue is that public transport connects the main towns and villages of the province, while numerous small villages and valleys remain isolated.

Another challenge is **traffic congestion**, particularly on the A22 motorway, especially during peak tourist seasons and holiday periods. This congestion not only affects travel times but also contributes to environmental pollution.

Another one is **maintaining and upgrading infrastructure** in the face of natural hazards such as landslides and heavy snowfall, which are common in this mountainous region. Ensuring the safety and reliability of transport routes requires substantial investment and continuous monitoring.

Furthermore, promoting **sustainable transport** remains a priority. While the region has made strides in developing bike lanes and promoting public transport, increasing the adoption of electric vehicles and enhancing green transport options are ongoing challenges.

The **healthcare system** in Trentino is integrated into Italy's broader national framework, which operates across multiple territorial levels. According to the Italian Constitution, health protection is a shared responsibility between the state and regional governments. While the state sets the essential health services to be guaranteed nationwide, regions, like Trentino and Abruzzo, independently manage and organize healthcare within their borders.

The healthcare system in Trentino is managed autonomously through the Provincial Agency for Health Services (*Azienda Provinciale per i Servizi Sanitari*, APSS). The network includes **seven public hospitals**, with the largest being Santa Chiara Hospital in Trento, which acts as a regional reference point, alongside others in Rovereto, Cavalese, Tione, and Borgo Valsugana. Trentino also boasts a robust extra-hospital care network, comprising **254 facilities** (Crea Sanità, 2018). These facilities include

outpatient clinics, laboratories, semi-residential structures (such as psychiatric day centres), and residential facilities like 50 Residenze Sanitarie Assistenziali (RSAs)¹⁴ - which focus on elderly and non-self-sufficient patients - and hospices. These facilities are operated by a mix of public and private (accredited by the APSS) entities.

This network has expanded from 211 facilities in 2013. The private sector plays a significant role in extra-hospital care, operating 59% of outpatient facilities, 66% of semi-residential structures, and 77% of residential facilities. Provincial healthcare policies prioritize integrating hospital and territorial services to address the needs of an aging population and future demographic growth (Crea Sanità, 2018).

Taking a closer look at the data (see Table 10), the healthcare system in the Autonomous Province of Trento reflects significant regional variations in the distribution of facilities and resources. At the provincial level, in 2021, there were **13 healthcare facilities and 1,979 available hospital beds**.

Focusing on the two territories selected for the MAP, the data shows that in the **Vallagarina** community valley (Table 12) there were 2 healthcare facilities and 397 hospital beds available in 2021, highlighting a moderate level of healthcare provision. In contrast, the **Alta Valsugana** (Table 13) community valley had no healthcare facilities, and no hospital beds reported for the same year. This stark difference emphasizes the uneven allocation of healthcare resources within the province, with Vallagarina equipped to serve its residents locally, while those in Alta Valsugana may need to rely on facilities in other areas.

Trentino's **education system** demonstrates significant strengths, particularly in early childhood education, supported by substantial investments and initiatives aimed at reducing educational disparities. In 2020, the region offered **37.9 nursery places per 100 children aged 0-2 years**, far exceeding the national average of 27.2% and surpassing the EU benchmark of 33% (Openpolis, 2022a). The city of Trento stands out with 43.4 nursery places per 100 children, alongside municipalities like Rovereto and Pergine Valsugana, where coverage also exceeds 40% (Openpolis, 2022a).

Taking a closer look at the data (Table 11), Trentino stands out for its strong commitment to building an inclusive and well-structured education system that supports learners from early childhood to higher education. The region hosts **608 schools**, ensuring widespread access to education across all levels. Early childhood education receives significant attention, with **267 nursery schools** serving over 17,000 children. This includes 3,743 children aged 0-3 years and 13,453 aged 3-6 years, highlighting the region's focus on providing a solid foundation for lifelong learning. These figures exceed national averages, reflecting Trentino's emphasis on the critical role of early education in cognitive and social

¹⁴ Data retrieved from the Autonomous Province of Trento website dedicated to health services: <https://www.trentinosalute.net/Arree-tematiche/Anziani/Residenze-sanitarie-assistenziali-RSA-in-Trentino/Informazioni-sulle-RSA>

development¹⁵. As students progress, the system remains robust, with **209 primary schools, 82 lower secondary schools, and 50 upper secondary schools**. The distribution aligns with demographic trends, ensuring continuity in education while accommodating shrinking cohorts at higher levels.

With regard to the two territories selected as MAPs, Vallagarina and Alta Valsugana community valleys, the data show notable contrasts that reflect broader regional trends in education. In **Vallagarina** (Table 12), there are 47 schools, including 27 primary schools, 12 lower secondary schools, and 8 upper secondary schools. By comparison, **Alta Valsugana** (Table 13) hosts 311 schools, including 22 primary schools, 6 lower secondary schools, and 8 upper secondary schools.

Trentino hosts the **University of Trento**, founded in 1962 by Provincial President Bruno Kessler. The university, with around 17,000 students¹⁶ (Università di Trento), is medium-sized but internationally renowned. It includes departments such as Economics and Management, Law, Humanities and Philosophy, Engineering, Sociology, Mathematics, Physics and Natural Sciences, and Cognitive Sciences (located in Rovereto).

There are also some research centers, specialized in different topics. In addition to EURICSE, (founded in 2008 through an initiative led by the University of Trento, the Trentino Federation of Cooperation, the Autonomous Province of Trento, the Foundation for Savings and Loans of Trento and Rovereto (Caritro) and the International Co-operative Alliance), in the 1960s, the Province also established the Trentino Institute of Culture, which in 2007 became the **Bruno Kessler Foundation**. This foundation operates two scientific-technological centres (Materials and Microsystems, and Information Technology - FBK-irst), two humanities centers (the Italian-German Historical Institute - FBK-isig, and the Institute for Religious Studies - FBK-is), and the European Center for Theoretical Studies in Nuclear Physics and Related Areas (ECT*).

Trento is also home to the **Centre for Computational and Systems Biology (CoSBI)**, a bioinformatics research hub specializing in pharmaceuticals and nutrigenomics, created through a partnership involving the Italian government, the Autonomous Province of Trento, the University of Trento, and Microsoft. Additionally, the Alpine Ecology Center merged in 2008 with the **Edmund Mach Foundation**, continuing the legacy of the **San Michele all'Adige Agricultural Institute**, a center for secondary education, research, and technical support in agriculture.

Table 11 Healthcare & Educational services in the Autonomous Province of Trento. Selected indicators.

Selected indicators	Abs./Rel. No.	Year of reference
Number of schools ^a , of which:	608	S.Y. 2021/2022
Nursery schools	267	
Primary schools	209	

¹⁵ As also highlighted in Table 18, the nursery school service (0-3 years and 3-6 years) is also guaranteed by a significant presence of social economy organizations. Furthermore, instead of nursery school, families have the possibility of sending their children aged between 0 and 2 years to a *Tagesmutter* (which literally means “day mother” in German). This service – offered by the Autonomous Province of Trento in collaboration with social economy organizations – is a “family nursery”, a place where a person takes care of a maximum of 5 children in their own home or in rooms rented by them. Anyone can offer this service, but to obtain the care permit it is necessary to attend a training course and respect some basic rules.

¹⁶ Data retrieved from the University of Trento website: <https://www.unitn.it/ateneo/5/unitrento-in-numeri>

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<i>Lower secondary schools</i>	82	
<i>Upper secondary school</i>	50	
Pupils enrolled in early childhood education, of which:	17,196	S.Y. 2021/2022 - 2022/2023
<i>0-3 years^{1,b}</i>	3,743	S.Y. 2022/2023
<i>3-6 years^c</i>	13,453	S.Y. 2021/2022
Enrolment Ratio in Tertiary Education ^{2,d}	38.7%	2022
Number of healthcare facilities	13	2021
Available beds in hospitals ^{3,e}	1,979	2021

Sources:

- Data aggregated from ISTAT (2024). Istruzione e Formazione. Scuole. <http://dati.istat.it/>
- ISPAT (2024). I servizi socio-educativi per la prima infanzia in Trentino. http://www.statistica.provincia.tn.it/binary/pat_statistica_new/istruzione_formazione/ServiziSocioEducativiInfanziaTrentino_2022_2023.1709108766.pdf
- Data from ISTAT (2024). Istruzione e Formazione. Scuole. <http://dati.istat.it/>
- ISTAT (2023). ANNUARIO STATISTICO ITALIANO 2023. ISTAT. https://www.istat.it/storage/ASI/2023/ASI_2023.pdf
- Data from ISTAT (2024). Salute e sanità. Servizi sanitari e loro ricorso. Istituti di cura. <http://dati.istat.it/>

Notes:

- Mean of pupils enrolled by month in the reference school year. August was not considered in the calculation of the mean.
- The percentage of young adults aged 19-25 enrolled in university and residing within the same region. Data refers to 01/01/2022.
- Beds in general inpatient care.

Table 12 Healthcare & Educational services in Vallagarina. Selected indicators.

Selected indicators	Abs./Rel. No.	Year of reference
Number of schools ^a , of which:	47 ¹	S.Y. 2021/2022
<i>Nursery schools</i>	n/a	
<i>Primary schools</i>	27	
<i>Lower secondary schools</i>	12	
<i>Upper secondary school</i>	8	
Pupils enrolled in early childhood education, of which:	n/a	-
<i>0-3 years</i>	n/a	-
<i>3-6 years</i>	n/a	-
Enrolment Ratio in Tertiary Education	n/a	-
Number of healthcare facilities ^b	2	2021
Available beds in hospitals ^b	397	2021

Sources:

- ISPAT (2023). I percorsi formativi e lavorativi dei giovani in Trentino: un'analisi esplorativa. http://www.statistica.provincia.tn.it/binary/pat_statistica_new/istruzione_formazione/PercorsiFormativiLavorativiGiovaniTrentino_completo.1703760045.pdf
- Data from ISTAT (2024). Salute e sanità. Servizi sanitari e loro ricorso. Istituti di cura. <http://dati.istat.it/>

Notes:

- Data on nursery schools are not available therefore this figure may underestimate the total number of schools in the area.

Table 13 Healthcare & Educational services in Alta Valsugana. Selected indicators.

Selected indicators	Abs./Rel. No.	Year of reference
Number of schools ^a , of which:	31 ¹	S.Y. 2021/2022
<i>Nursery schools</i>	n/a	
<i>Primary schools</i>	22	
<i>Lower secondary schools</i>	6	
<i>Upper secondary school</i>	8	
Pupils enrolled in early childhood education, of which:	n/a	-
<i>0-3 years</i>	n/a	-
<i>3-6 years</i>	n/a	-
Enrolment Ratio in Tertiary Education	n/a	-
Number of healthcare facilities ^b	0	2021
Available beds in hospitals ^b	0	2021

Sources:

- a) ISPAT (2023). *I percorsi formativi e lavorativi dei giovani in Trentino: un'analisi esplorativa*. Ispat. http://www.statistica.provincia.tn.it/binary/pat_statistica_new/istruzione_istruzione_formazione/PercorsiFormativiLavorativiGiovaniTrentino_completo.1703760045.pdf
- b) Data from ISTAT (2024). *Salute e sanità. Servizi sanitari e loro ricorso. Istituti di cura*. <http://dati.istat.it/>

Notes:

1. Data on nursery schools are not available therefore this figure may underestimate the total number of schools in the area.

4.6 Local policies and instruments

To cope with the specific challenges of rural areas, the Autonomous Province of Trento – like other regions in Italy – benefits from several national and European strategies aimed at fostering local development:

- Trentino participates in the **National Strategy for Inner Areas** aiming to improve transportation, healthcare, education, and economic opportunities in these areas. There are only two selected areas: Val di Sole and Tesino;
- Trentino implements measures from the **National Rural Development Program** (*Programma di Sviluppo Rurale Nazionale - PSRN*)¹⁷. This includes support for sustainable agriculture, modernization of farms, young farmer initiatives, and improvements to rural infrastructure.
- Trentino benefits from the **European Structural and Investment Funds** (ESIF), particularly through the ERDF and the ESF, which support various regional development projects, including infrastructure improvements, business support, training and employment initiatives, and environmental sustainability.
- The **National Fund for Rural Development** provides additional financial support to complement EU funding, helping to finance rural development projects such as enhancing rural infrastructure, promoting tourism, supporting local enterprises, and environmental conservation in Trentino.

¹⁷ PSRN is co-financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).

- Trentino participates in the **LEADER program**, with two LAGs operating in the region¹⁸. These groups develop and implement local development strategies tailored to the specific needs of their communities, focusing on improving rural services, promoting local products, fostering tourism, and preserving cultural heritage.
- Trentino is involved in **Smart Villages initiatives**, promoting digital innovation and connectivity in rural areas. These projects aim to enhance digital services, support local businesses, and improve the quality of life for residents by leveraging new technologies.
- **Agri-environmental measures** are actively implemented in Trentino, encouraging sustainable farming practices that protect biodiversity, water resources, and soil quality. These measures help preserve the natural environment while promoting sustainable agricultural practices.
- Trentino supports **renewable energy projects**, including bioenergy, solar, and wind energy initiatives. These projects promote sustainable energy use, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and create local employment opportunities in the green energy sector.

As emerged from the interviews, the differentiating factor between rural areas in Trentino and most rural areas in other Italian regions is that the Province of Trento enjoys an **autonomous status**. As stated by several interviewees, thanks to local taxation – which remains local – it is possible to keep communities alive even in areas where a national taxation system would not allow it. Moreover, thanks to **Valley Communities**, public bodies - and especially mayors - have been able to maintain a close, capillary relationship even with the most peripheral territories.

Box 2 presents one interesting initiative implemented in the Autonomous Province of Trento with the aim of fostering local economic development and enhancing local well-being in rural and mountain areas: consumer cooperative stores with the status of Services of General Economic Interest.

Box 2 Consumer cooperatives and Services of General Economic Interest

What is a SGEI?

Services of general interest (SGI) are services that public authorities of the European member States classify as being of general interest and, therefore, are subject to specific public service obligations. They can be provided either by the State or by the private sector.

Services of general interest are classified into three categories, among which there are Services of General Economic Interest (SGEI), i.e., basic services that are carried out in return for payment, such as postal services. These services are subject to European internal market and competition rules. However, there may be derogations to these rules if necessary to protect citizens' access to basic services.

¹⁸ GAL Trentino Orientale for the eastern area, which includes the Communities of Primiero, Valsugana and Tesino, Alta Valsugana and Bersntol, and Altipiani Cimbri and GAL Trentino Centrale for the central area - which includes the Communities of Valle dei Laghi, Rotaliana-Königsberg, and Valle di Cembra.

In Trentino, multi-service stores that offer not only food and basic necessities, but also a range of essential community services, may qualify as SGEI. In order to be qualified as an SGEI, a store has to satisfy some conditions:

- the store must be located above 500 MASL¹⁹;
- the location must have at least 100 inhabitants;
- the store must be at a minimum distance of 3 km of road from the closest store²⁰;
- there must be no other store in the location;
- the registered office must be in Trentino;
- the area of the store must be between 50 and 300 square meters;
- daily opening hours of at least 3 hours for at least 6 days a week, or 5 days, of which at least one must be open both in the morning and in the afternoon for a total of at least 6 hours divided between morning and afternoon;
- the turnover of the store must be below EUR 591,560;
- Annual Working Units (AWU) must be below 2.5;
- the store must be located outside historical places of trade.

A SGEI must provide at least 4 services, 2 of which are considered to be most in the public interest (1-8), from a list of 18 services (Provincial Law 1958/2022):

- 1 services provided in agreement with public bodies;
- 2 free assistance service for telephone or online booking of specialist medical examinations;
- 3 free medical report printing service and assistance in accessing the citizen's medical record;
- 4 free drug delivery point service;
- 5 free centre service for the collection and subsequent dispatch of mail in towns without a post office;
- 6 payment services (e.g. utility bills);
- 7 free grocery delivery service;
- 8 ATM service;
- 9 selling meat;
- 10 free internet access via Wi-Fi network;
- 11 free parcel pick-up point service;

¹⁹ This principle can be derogated in case of severe isolation.

²⁰ This principle can be derogated in case of severe isolation.

- 12 telephone top-up service of at least two major mobile phone operators;
- 13 sale of daily newspapers and magazines;
- 14 free Internet and e-mail access via a PC workstation, free fax and photocopying service open to the public;
- 15 sale of at least ten organic and/or coeliac products;
- 16 sale of at least ten products from Trentino and/or fair-trade products;
- 17 bicycle rental service;
- 18 free battery charging service for electric bicycles.

Genesis of SGEI in Trentino

Due to their remote location and mergers of consumer cooperatives that took place in the '90s, that reduced the available *de minimis* contribution per store (within the same cooperative), many stores in mountainous areas were facing the risk of failing. Despite their crucial role in supporting the communities in remote areas of the Province, these stores were not economically sustainable.

In 2017 the Autonomous Province of Trento and the Federazione Trentina della Cooperazione addressed the European Commission to intervene in the State Aid regulation to support the stores that represent a unique presence in mountainous areas. After a positive response from the Commission, the Province Council, with the 18 May 2018 Resolution, identified and defined the SIEG for mountain areas, access criteria and implementation modalities.

Current state of SGEI

Today, in the Autonomous Province of Trento there are 124 SGEI, from the original 58 in 2018, and the *de minimis* maximum has been raised to EUR 750,000 in 2024 from the previous EUR 500,000.

SGEI operate emphasizing the necessity of local stakeholder engagement, especially municipalities, coherently with a social economy approach. They play a crucial role in providing basic services to most isolated communities, targeting especially the elderly for whom it would be impossible to reach stores located outside their area. For instance, for persons with reduced mobility, the grocery delivery service can guarantee access to basic products without relying on relatives. Payment services offer a support to the elderly who are not computer literate.

Recognition of SGEI

The case of SGEI in Trentino was presented in a series of seminars and meetings in Rome, Bologna, Verona and Brussels, as well as at the International Conference "Economia Sociale: la Persona al Centro" (*Social Economy: the Person at the Centre*) organised in 2022 in Trento by the Province and the Ministry of Labour and of Social Policies.

In November 2023, at a seminar organised by the European Association of Service Providers for Persons with Disabilities (EASPD), the case of SGEI was presented as a good practice from which to take inspiration also in other Member States.

Source:

Sforzi, J. & Berton, A. (2019). *La cooperazione di consumo e i SIEG*. In C. Carini & E. Fontanari (Eds). *La cooperazione in Trentino. Punti di forza e sfide per l'economia locale*. Euricse Research Report, n. 17/19, EURICSE, Trento, p. 55-68.

Cooperazione Trentina (2024). *Oltre la spesa. Servizi per la comunità*.

<https://www.infederazione.it/media/gfwbpsn5/brochure-sieg.pdf>

4.7 Strategies fostering social inclusion in rural areas

The Autonomous Province of Trento has implemented several policies and initiatives to promote social inclusion in its rural areas, addressing various vulnerabilities and supporting the well-being of its residents. These strategies operate within a framework that emphasizes **sustainable development, community engagement, and economic empowerment** and some of them explicitly target vulnerable groups, including the elderly, migrants, low-income families, and individuals with disabilities.

The current social inclusion strategies in Trentino are part of a **long-term plan**, typically spanning five to ten years, with periodic evaluations and adjustments to ensure effectiveness. The primary focus of these strategies includes improving access to essential services, enhancing educational and employment opportunities, and fostering community cohesion. These efforts aim to reduce disparities between urban and rural areas, ensuring that all residents can benefit from the region's economic growth. Key initiatives include:

- **Rural development programs**, which focus on improving infrastructure, healthcare, and education in rural areas. They aim to create a supportive environment that allows vulnerable populations to thrive.
- **Employment and training programs**, which target unemployed and underemployed individuals and provide vocational training, job placement services, and support for entrepreneurship, helping residents gain stable and meaningful employment.
- **Social housing projects**, which provide affordable housing solutions for low-income families and individuals facing housing insecurity, ensuring that they have access to safe and stable living conditions.
- **Community engagement and integration projects**, which are designed to foster social cohesion and include cultural activities, language courses for migrants, and community-building events that promote inclusiveness and mutual understanding.

The Autonomous Province of Trento plays a central role in designing and implementing these policies, often in collaboration with local municipalities. NGOs and community organizations, such as

Fondazione Caritro²¹ and Associazione Trentina Accoglienza Stranieri (ATAS) Onlus²², provide critical support and expertise, especially in outreach and direct service provision. Table 14 presents the key actors and strategies/initiatives to promote social inclusion in rural areas.

Table 14 Key actors and strategies/initiatives to promote social inclusion in rural areas of Trentino

Actor/Initiative	Description
Social Cooperatives	They play a crucial role in providing social services, creating job opportunities for disadvantaged groups, and fostering social integration in rural areas.
Third Sector and Volunteering Initiatives	They include projects that provide social care, educational support, and community development activities in rural areas.
Family and Community Support Programs	E.g., “Family Audit” and “Family Districts”, which aim to create family-friendly environments by providing support services (e.g., childcare services) and enhancing the quality of life for families in rural areas.
Inclusive Education Initiatives	Aimed at ensuring access to quality education for all, including those in rural areas through e.g., transportation for students from remote areas, digital education tools, and special support for students with disabilities.
Health and Social Care Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National health plan: includes specific measures to improve healthcare access in rural areas; - Telemedicine: expansion of telemedicine services to provide healthcare in remote areas, reducing the need for travel and improving access to medical consultations.
Digital inclusion programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Broadband expansion: national initiatives to expand broadband access in rural areas to bridge the digital divide; - Digital literacy: programs to enhance digital skills among rural populations, ensuring they can access online services and opportunities.
Migrant and Refugee Integration Programs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National and EU-funded programs aim to integrate migrants and refugees into rural communities through language courses, job training, and community-building activities; - Local support for local governments and organizations to develop tailored integration plans that meet the specific needs of rural areas.

From the analysis of the interviews, what clearly emerges is the difficulty for the Autonomous Province of Trento in **decentralising decision-making processes**, thus creating initiatives and services that are tailored-made for the territory in which they are planned to be implemented. Indeed, while most interviewees highly appreciate the existing tools and policies, some local stakeholders feel they are not sufficiently tailored to the unique needs and resources of the territory. The words of one interviewee explain this well:

I would say that the difficulty is decentralisation [...]. We [the Autonomous Province of Trento] centralise a lot... we have important services and then we bring them to the territory, but we bring them as already pre-established. The municipality's activity of subsidiarity and the possibility of customising services for the specific territories is limited. [...] [It would be useful] to transfer the decision-making process to the periphery.

Working directly in the territories is seen as a winning strategy, as stated by an interviewee: *I believe that the strategy of working in the territories [...] is important so that protection networks [for vulnerable people] are guaranteed, also in terms of prevention. [Adhering to the principle of*

²¹ Fondazione Caritro website: <https://www.fondazione-caritro.it/>

²² ATAS Onlus website: <http://www.atas.tn.it/>

*territoriality gives] the possibility of involving citizens and the various organisations in the best possible way [...]. **A local presence throughout the territory is a precious resource to be valued.***

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5. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the region

With reference to Trentino's rural areas, the analysis of the interviews with local stakeholders highlights the specific weaknesses that qualify these areas as disadvantaged. Below are the main reasons reported by interviewees:

- **Demographic factors**, in particular the demographic decline²³ and the progressive ageing of the population, with numerous consequences on both the economic and social fabric of the territory. Indeed, these demographic shifts are regarded as factors that further contribute to the social, economic and cultural marginalisation of rural areas.
- **Lack of/excessive distance from essential services** (e.g., education, socio-health and cultural services). The geographic isolation and low population density of rural areas may make the provision of some essential services economically unviable. In turn, the lack of services contributes to making these areas less liveable (especially for families with children and elderly people), further contributing to their depopulation.

Social and health services deserve specific attention, as most of the interviewees consider their provision in rural areas unsuitable, mainly due to the lack of health facilities and the inadequate number of trained health professionals. A good - albeit partial - indicator to measure this lack of services is the average travel time between the place of residence and the emergency room. According to Agenas – the National Agency for Regional Social Services – data (2024), in Trentino Alto-Adige, 8.06% of the population (compared to 2.58% of the national average) has difficulty accessing the emergency room within 30 minutes.²⁴

- **Education**, as in rural and mountainous areas, access to education is perceived by interviewees as more difficult, starting with nursery school and moving on to higher education. Not only the general lack of these services is emphasised, but also the more inadequate level of the educational offer, which in turn has an impact on the level of learning and the educational capital of students.
- **Culture**, as rural areas are perceived as rich in terms of cultural (as well as natural) heritage but, at the same time, there is a lack of initiatives and facilities, such as museums, theatres, libraries and centres for cultural aggregation.

²³ The analysis of the interviews confirms the demographic decline, especially in rural areas. However, some stakeholders interviewed highlight a (although weak) trend reversal: the recent enhancement of peripheral activities, such as organic mountain farming, which are seen as more and more attractive, and the presence of generous incentives for such activities have attracted many young people to rural areas. Moreover, compared to the past, the availability of technology has reduced the isolation of people living in these areas. Lastly, the lower cost of living compared to urban areas is mentioned as an element that encourages people to return to these areas.

²⁴ Data for the Autonomous Province of Trento is not publicly available. For further information, see the webpage dedicated to the Agenas event "Accessi in Pronto Soccorso e Implementazione DM 77/2022 per una migliore presa in carico dei pazienti" (Rome, 22/04/2024) and in particular the presentation by Dr. Maria Pia Randazzo: <https://www.agenas.gov.it/comunicazione/primo-piano/2413-22-aprile-%E2%80%93-evento-agenas-accessi-in-pronto-soccorso-e-implementazione-dm-77-2022-per-una-migliore-presa-in-carico-dei-pazienti>

- **Limited access to infrastructures**, in particular:
 - **Ultra-wideband connectivity**: according to some interviewees, internet coverage and the – sometimes very poor – quality of connections represent a peculiar challenge for some Trentino territories, limiting opportunities for the development of remote work and online business activities. Indeed, most municipalities in Trentino are located in white areas, i.e., areas where there is no broadband network coverage. Since 2016, the provincial government, in agreement with the national government, has allocated EUR 44.7 million from the Ministry for Economic Development, plus EUR 25 million in provincial contributions, to guarantee ultra-broadband in white areas of Trentino.
 - **Mobility/Logistics/Transportation**: limited road network, lack of rail connections (or presence of outdated infrastructures) and lack of alternative mobility solutions negatively affect the quality of life in these areas. The morphological structure of the territory is considered to be one of the main reasons for the mobility and transport problems in these areas. Moreover, public transport services in some of these areas may be insufficient, with few daily trips and inadequate geographical coverage.
- **Lack of employment opportunities**, as rural areas of Trentino are highly dependent on the agricultural sector and in particular on the cultivation of apples and grapes. The lack of employment alternatives due to the area's lower attractiveness for investment forces many people, especially young people, to migrate to urban areas. Moreover, as one interviewee states, “in a peripheral area, the quality of work is lower”: for example, jobs – especially in the agricultural sector – often tend to be more precarious, wages are lower, training and development opportunities for human resources are scarce and the technological endowment of companies is poorer. This, besides being a critical element for those working in these areas, limits the ability of these territories to attract new workers.

5.1 Social exclusion and poverty

In the province of Trento, more than 225,000 people were employed as of June 2024, showing a significant increase from previous years. The unemployment rate fell from 3.4% to 3.2% between 2023 and 2024, placing Trentino among the Italian regions with the lowest unemployment rates. This positive trend underscores the resilience of the local labor market, supported by targeted policies to stimulate job creation and economic stability (Agenzia del Lavoro, 2024).

When looking at economic disparities, however, the data reveal some fragilities within the territory. About 7% of the population was at risk of poverty in 2023, still showing a modest improvement from 7.5% in 2022. This figure suggests gradual progress in reducing economic insecurity, but highlights ongoing challenges, particularly among low-income households and immigrant communities, who face disproportionate levels of financial instability and social exclusion (Fenalt, 2024; Provincia di Trento, 2024).

The province's economy remains highly dependent on key sectors such as trade, hospitality, and agriculture, as these industries contribute significantly to local employment, particularly in what

concerns with seasonal work playing an important role, especially in the more strictly mountainous areas that depend heavily on tourism (Agenzia del Lavoro, 2024).

As for the social assistance system in Trentino, this offers a wide range of support programs to meet different needs. Unemployment benefits, such as NASpl, provide crucial assistance to people facing job loss, while housing grants aim to ease the burden of rising living costs. Disability pensions and targeted support for individuals with severe disabilities are also a significant part of the welfare framework, ensuring that vulnerable populations have access to essential resources (Agenzia del Lavoro, 2024). The welfare system also includes family support measures, such as child benefits and parental leave schemes, which aim to promote work-life balance and provide financial relief to families. The introduction of universal child benefits has increased the number of beneficiaries, contributing to improved financial stability for households with children. Furthermore, public health and social care services play a vital role in supporting individuals with chronic illnesses or disabilities, ensuring access to healthcare and rehabilitation programs (Provincia di Trento, 2024).

5.2 Disadvantaged groups

Before moving to the description of the main groups of the population that may be regarded as vulnerable in the Autonomous Province of Trento, it is necessary to make three important preliminary remarks. First, the vast majority of local stakeholders interviewed underline that the categories of people at risk of social exclusion/already experiencing situations of social exclusion are **constantly changing over time**. Recent changes such as the COVID-19 pandemic, as well as the war in Ukraine and the ensuing energy crisis, have exacerbated existing inequalities and created new pockets of deprivation. Alongside the classic categories, such as the elderly, people with disabilities (PWDs) and the unemployed, there is a constant emergence of new groups of people living in contexts characterised by poverty, social marginalisation and lack of access to services.

Secondly, as mentioned by one interviewee, besides specific groups of the population, in rural and peripheral areas, **the communities themselves are vulnerable** and at risk of exclusion. Population-decline and ageing trends, migrations to urban centres for better educational and employment opportunities, disinvestments in local infrastructures and closure of local shops are all factors that significantly contribute to explaining the vulnerability of these areas as a whole.

Lastly, several interviewees emphasise one need that is shared by many inhabitants of rural and peripheral areas, regardless of their specific status as fragile persons: **the need for sociability**. Indeed, according to an interviewee, the inherent human tendency towards sociability is particularly developed in small villages: the isolation of the territory is contrasted by a distinctly social attitude of its inhabitants. This is testified by an episode reported by one interviewee, director of a *Famiglia Cooperativa* (consumers cooperative) that has several stores in rural areas. One of them needed renovation and was therefore closed for a short time. Before the renovation started, the coffee machine at the entrance of the store was taken away temporarily. Upon seeing that the coffee machine was about to be taken away, a customer asked the manager to reposition the coffee machine after renovation, emphasising its function as a “meeting point” for the community.

Having said so, in the Autonomous Province of Trento, different groups of the population may be regarded as vulnerable: **NEETs, women, people with disabilities (PWDs), immigrants and the elderly**. The sections below describe, for each of these categories, their main characteristics, the causes behind their vulnerability, how the vulnerability is affecting their life conditions and opportunities and the main challenges they face. Statistical data are complemented with information emerged from the interviews carried out with local stakeholders.

5.2.1 NEETs

In 2022, NEETs (Not in Education, Employment, or Training) ²⁵ in Trentino accounted for **11.1%**. A decrease compared to the data for 2021 (17.6%) is noticeable. The incidence of NEETs in Trentino is significantly lower than the national figure (19.0%) and in line with the share in the European Union (11.7%) (ISPAT, 2023a).

While data show a slight decrease in the number of young people in a NEET situation, the perception of the interviewees is that their number – as well as the number of young people who require psychological/psychoanalytical support because they have difficulties, especially relational ones, and are therefore more at risk of becoming NEETs – is increasing. Some interviewees attribute the **increase in cases of social exclusion** in this category to the COVID-19 pandemic: the return to face-to-face relationships, after two years of mainly online relationships, was problematic for many of these young people.

While the situation in the Autonomous Province of Trento is somewhat better compared to the national average due to stronger local economic conditions and better educational outcomes, there are still challenges. This demographic is often characterized by a variety of factors, including **socioeconomic disadvantages, lack of access to quality education**, and sometimes even **mental health issues**.

The Autonomous Province of Trento has recognized the importance of addressing the NEET phenomenon and has implemented several initiatives aimed at improving NEET employability and facilitating their entry into the labour market. Box 3 presents one of the most recent and most promising projects addressing this category: **the C.O.P.E. project**.

Box 3 C.O.P.E. project

What is C.O.P.E.?

C.O.P.E. (*Capabilities, Opportunities, Places and Engagement*) is a project funded by the European Commission under the Employment and Social Innovation (EaSI) programme. It involves 7 partners from 4 different European countries, and it aims to develop social and occupational inclusion activities for NEETs from 15 to 34 years old.

²⁵ NEET refers to individuals, typically aged 15-29, who are disengaged from the labour market and educational systems. In some cases, it is extended to young people up to the age of 34, if they are still cohabiting with their parents.

The project, which started in January 2022 and ended in June 2024, engages 600 vulnerable youngsters in Italy and Portugal to promote their autonomy, social and occupational inclusion and wellbeing. In particular, it focuses especially on:

- Women,
- Youth with disabilities,
- Youth from a migratory background,
- Youth with a low level of education,
- Youth from low-income families,
- Youth from isolated and peripheral areas.

Based on the initial situation of the young person, the aim is to:

- Find an occupation,
- Get the labour market closer,
- Start a training course.

Two different paths are envisaged in the project: Path 1 targets young NEETs who are inactive but currently ready to enter the labour market, while Path 2 targets those who are still not ready to enter. This differentiated approach is designed to better address the complex variety of needs and constraints that NEETs exhibit.

In Italy, C.O.P.E. project has been promoted by the Autonomous Province of Trento (Department of Health and Social Policies - Research and Innovation Office), the Trentino Federation of Cooperatives (FTC), the Provincial Agency for Health Services (*Azienda Provinciale per i Servizi Sanitari*, APSS), and the social cooperative Co.ge.s Don Milani. The project focuses on the whole territory of the Autonomous Province of Trento.

Social Prescribing and Link Workers

The methodological framework adopted in the project is social prescribing. Originally developed in the field of general medicine, it has been adapted to fit the social inclusion purpose of the C.O.P.E project and Trentino specificities. The objective of the social prescribing approach in C.O.P.E is to activate the territorial proximity network. The central figure this methodology envisages is the Link Worker. Link Workers – who usually come from social economy organisations or the public sector – act as a bridge between the users and the community and follow the NEETs in their tailored path to enhance existing resources and activate unexpressed ones, both of users, territories and proximity networks. Thus, the required characteristics of a Link Worker are: socio-educational background, empathy, training and a deep knowledge of the organizations operating in the territory, especially the ones of the Third sector.

To facilitate Link Workers' tasks, FTC developed the STARTin' platform, which allows to engage the users in the activities of the project, map the available resources in the area and connect users with available job and training opportunities.

C.O.P.E. goals

Project goals are to:

- Improve the enjoyment of civil and economic rights,
- Find employment for at least 60% of the users in Path 1,
- Engage at least 80% of the recipients in an individual path of social and occupational inclusion,
- Gain results of social inclusion for at least 60% of the users in Path 2.

C.O.P.E. seeks to create a network of territorial hubs that ensure access to services to youngsters through Link Workers. Moreover, the project laid the foundation for the creation of community workshops for the social economy and the exploitation of digital tools to reach young people and facilitate their social and labour inclusion.

For more information, see the C.O.P.E. project website: <https://copeproject.eu/>

Moreover, there are targeted efforts to integrate NEETs into the **cooperative sector**, which is – as previously recalled – a significant part of Trentino's economy. By leveraging the strong tradition of cooperatives in the region, young people can find supportive environments that offer both employment and personal development opportunities. Cooperatives – and especially social cooperatives – often provide mentorship and training, helping NEETs to gain practical skills and build professional networks. However, as pointed out by one respondent, for some young people “the social cooperative creates a stigma because social cooperatives are perceived as enterprises targeting only problematic people and therefore not for everyone”. The world of **associations**, perceived as more “neutral” than that of social cooperatives, could play an even more prominent role in offering young people opportunities for socialising and, at the same time, learning opportunities (especially soft skills).

Educational institutions in Trentino are also playing a vital role by creating pathways for continuous learning and skill acquisition. Partnerships between schools, universities, social economy organisations (SEOs) and local businesses aim to align educational outcomes with market needs, ensuring that young people are better prepared for the workforce.

5.2.2 Women

In 2023, there were 275,315 women in the Autonomous Province of Trento, representing 50.7% of the population²⁶. On average, women in Trentino are more educated than men: for about half of the men,

²⁶ Data from ISTAT (2023) Popolazione e famiglie. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

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their higher educational attainment is a lower secondary diploma or a professional qualification (corresponding to ISCED 2), while **women attain higher qualifications**. For instance, a quarter of Trentino women (compared to 18% of men) hold a university degree (Provincia Autonoma di Trento, 2020)²⁷.

Despite being more educated than men, according to ISTAT data in 2024 **employed women in Trentino are considerably less than men**: 65.1% against 74.4%. Also, the inactivity rate is higher for women (32.6%) than for men (23.7%)²⁸.

Regarding the issue of **gender-based violence**, data show that the situation in Trentino is roughly consistent with the national context. Considering the age group from 16 to 70, in 2014 19% of the women had suffered forms of physical violence in their lifetime (in more than half of the cases the aggressor was a partner or a former partner), while 3.4% in the last 12 months. In the same year, 23.3% of the women reported having been victims of sexual violence in their lives. In roughly a third of the cases, the aggressor was a partner or a former partner. The need for services and spaces dedicated to women – especially survivors of violence – has also been highlighted by some local stakeholders interviewed. More effort should be put into designing **awareness-raising and prevention campaigns** against gender-based violence.

5.2.3 People with disabilities

At the end of 2018, in the Autonomous Province of Trento, there were **28,201 people with disabilities** (APSS, 2019). This demographic includes a wide range of physical, sensory, intellectual, and psychological disabilities, each presenting unique challenges. As Table 15 shows, among PWDs, there was a prevalence of females (16,123, corresponding to 57.17%) and of people over 65 years old (13,880, corresponding to 58.22%).

Table 15 People with disabilities in the Autonomous Province of Trento by sex and age group (2018)

Age group	Male		Female		Total	
	N.	%	N.	%	N.	%
0-17	1,662	13.76	1,205	7.47	2,568	10.17
18-64	4,085	33.82	4,929	29.95	7,754	31.61
Over 65	6,331	52.54	10,089	62.58	13,880	58.22
Total	12,078	100.00	16,123	100.00	28,201	100.00

Source: APSS Trento (2019).

PWDs often encounter barriers when entering the **labour market**. Discrimination, lack of appropriate job accommodations, and insufficient support services can hinder their employment opportunities. Although there are policies in place to promote the inclusion of PWDs in the labour market, the implementation of these measures can be inconsistent.

Education and training opportunities for PWDs also require attention. Inclusive education practices are essential for ensuring that children with disabilities receive the same quality of education as their peers. Moreover, according to one stakeholder interviewed, a further limitation to the labour inclusion

²⁷ In 2018, considering the population of the Autonomous Province of Trento between 25 and 64 years old.

²⁸ Data from ISTAT (2024) Lavoro e Retribuzioni. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

opportunities of PWDs lies in the absence of connections between schools and the labour market: without proper transition programmes and support, PWDs entry into the labour market can be difficult, especially for those bearing severe disabilities. Lastly, the lack of tailored training and career counselling may result in a less smooth transition into the workforce.

Despite the region's proactive approach to social inclusion, PWDs in Trentino still face several obstacles. One of the primary challenges is **accessibility**. Although substantial progress has been made in making public spaces, transportation, and buildings more accessible, there are still areas that need improvement. Rural parts of Trentino, in particular, often lack the necessary infrastructure, making it difficult for individuals with disabilities to navigate their environments independently.

Lastly, the **social integration** of PWDs remains a complex issue. PWDs often face social isolation and stigmatization, which can impact their mental health and overall well-being. Community programs and initiatives aimed at fostering social inclusion are crucial, but more needs to be done to create a truly inclusive society.

Interestingly, for this category of vulnerable people rural areas could be regarded as a resource. According to one interviewee, it is indeed easier to create the conditions for PWDs' social and work inclusion in smaller contexts such as rural villages. Creating **welcoming communities**, which are therefore animated by actors that are sensitive to the needs and ready to make themselves available for the PWD and strengthening **proximity relations** are therefore strategies considered fundamental for improving the living conditions of this category.

5.2.4 Immigrants

According to the most recent available data (ISPAT, 2024b), the foreign population resident in Trentino amounts to over 47,000 people²⁹. They represent **8.6% of the total population** of the area, a percentage that is lower both compared with the national average (9.0%) and the average for the North-East Italian regions (11.2%)

The immigrant population is rather young: 20.2% are **below 18 years old**, while only 6.7% are over 65. Moreover, **women** are prevalent (52%) (ISPAT, 2024b). Most foreigners are **European citizens**. Romanians are the largest community (22.2% of total foreigners), followed by Albanians (11.0%), Moroccans and Pakistanis (both 7.5%) (ISPAT, 2024a; as of 01/01/2023).

As Table 16 shows, the distribution of foreign residents is not homogeneous across Valley Communities. Indeed, the three most populous communities comprise 57.5% of the foreign residents in Trentino: 29.66% in the Val d'Adige Territory, 17.46% in Vallagarina and 10.37% in Alto Garda and Ledro.

²⁹ As of 01/01/2024. Data are still preliminary. There has been an increase of 1 385 individuals (+3.0%) compared to 01/01/2023.

Table 16 Foreign resident population by Valley Community

Valley Community	N.	%
Val d'Adige	13,533	29.66
Vallagarina	7,963	17.46
Alto Garda e Ledro	4,732	10.37
Val di Non	3,717	8.15
Rotaliana-Königsberg	3,385	7.42
Alta Valsugana e Bersntol	3,321	7.28
Giudicarie	2,224	4.88
Valsugana e Tesino	1,704	3.74
Val di Fiemme	1,167	2.56
Valle di Sole	1,046	2.29
Valle dei Laghi	733	1.61
Comun General de Fascia	608	1.33
Valle di Cembra	600	1.32
Paganella	341	0.75
Primiero	296	0.65
Altipiani Cimbri	250	0.55
Autonomous Province of Trento	45,620	100.00

Source: ISPAT (2024a). Reference year: 2022

As emerged from the interviews, immigrants are even more fragile in rural areas and small municipalities. “In small communities – claimed an interviewee – what is different is viewed with distrust”. The risk is therefore that immigrants in rural areas are “isolated in an isolated context”. They often experience negative working conditions, i.e., illegal work or under an illegal gangmastering trade. It has also been reported that, especially with the younger generations of immigrants, it is often difficult to social workers experience severe difficulties in building labour and social integration paths for this group of disadvantaged workers as they show “very oppositional behaviour”, sometimes violent, and seem to have little desire to build a future in their host country.

At the same time, migrants can also represent a resource for rural areas, both to combat depopulation and the ageing of the population and to increase the workforce in these areas and start new processes of social innovation (Perlik et al., 2019; Fondazione Migrantes, 2020).

5.2.5 Elderly people

According to ISPAT data (ISPAT, 2023c), as of 1 January 2022, there were 123,916 people aged 65 and over (corresponding to 22.91% of the 540,958 total population) in Trentino. Among these, 68,552 (55.32%) were women.

As shown in Figure 8 and consistently with the scenario at the national level, the **55-59 age group** (1960s baby boom generation) is the most numerous, while the number of young people (the base of the pyramid in the figure) is smaller due to the falling birth rates in recent decades.

Figure 8 Population in the Autonomous Province of Trento by sex and age

Source: (ISPAT, 2023c). Reference year: 01/01/2022.

Notes: on the y-axis the age (in single years); on the x-axis the frequencies of males (left, in blue) and females (right, in red).

The **old-age index** – i.e., the ratio between the percentage of the population over 65 and young people up to the age of 14 – stands at 166.9. In other words, for every 100 young people there are approximately 167 elderly people. This index is significantly below the one at the national level (187.6) and the one referred to the North-East it stands (190.3)

In all the Valley Communities, the average age has increased compared to 2021. The increase ranges from 0.1 years in Vallagarina to 0.4 in Primiero and Comun General de Fascia.

In essence, data show a raising of the average age and a process of **population ageing**, which poses unique challenges. Indeed, this demographic shift places a substantial strain on public services, especially on the province’s healthcare system as older adults typically need more frequent medical attention and long-term care. Moreover, from an economic standpoint, the ageing population could lead to a shrinking workforce, affecting both the work and pension systems. Lastly, family and community dynamics may be affected too, as families (and especially women) are called to take care of elderly relatives and communities may experience accelerated decline as younger people tend to move to urban centres.

6. Assets and potentials in the region

From the analysis of the interviews, a clear and common element that emerges is the **sense of pride** felt towards the Trentino territory. Nearly all interviewees perceive Trentino as an area rich in various resources, from an environmental, economic, cultural, and social standpoint. Several interviewees describe Trentino as a "happy oasis", i.e., a region that – unlike others in Italy – remains flourishing and prosperous over the years. One interviewee emphasised this by pointing out the low migratory pressure leading people to leave Trentino:

Unlike other areas – especially in the South of Italy – where the push to migrate is very strong, it is difficult for a Trentino to leave [...] Compared to other regions, the percentage of people who move away is lower, and we are attractive because the standard of living is excellent.

Several factors contribute to these high standards of living. According to the interviewees, one key factor is the **rich and thriving nature** of the territory, which contributes to the citizens' sense of well-being. Moreover, the region's beauty, in terms of landscape, helps explain Trentino's success as a tourist destination for visitors from all over Italy and Europe.

Additionally, the vast majority of local stakeholders interviewed perceive the **public services** available in Trento as highly satisfactory, although there are some critical areas (especially in the health sector) that would require prompt intervention.

Another element that is regarded as an asset for the territory by local stakeholders interviewed is the **strong presence of social economy organisations** (SEOs) and in particular of associations, cooperatives and foundations. Table 17 presents ISTAT data on the number of SEOs and their employees registered in the Autonomous Province of Trento.

6.1 Strong social economy in the region

Table 17 Social economy organisations in the Autonomous Province of Trento

Legal forms	Social Economy Organisations*		Employees**	
	N.	%	N.	%
Associations	5,727	84.2	5,418	18.4
Cooperatives (other than social cooperatives)	331	4.8	14, 879	50.5
Social cooperatives	120	1.8	7,895	26.8
Foundations	96	1.4	508	1.7
Other legal forms***	528	7.8	787	2.7
Total	6,802	100.0	29,487	100.0

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT data: *Asia Imprese, Asia Occupazione, Censimento Istituzioni non-profit (2021)*.

* Data on organisations active in agriculture are not available. Thus, the figures reported in this table may underestimate the actual number of SEOs in Trentino.

** As of 31/12/2021 for all legal forms except for cooperatives (other than social cooperatives): annual average.

*** This category includes mutual aid societies; social enterprises with a legal form other than a cooperative; church bodies; and amateur sports clubs.

Association is the most prominent legal form among SEOs (5,727, corresponding to 84.2% of the total number of SEOs), and they employ more than 5,000 people. They mainly operate – as shown in Table 18 – in the Arts, entertainment and recreation sector. The importance of these SEOs for the territory is underlined also by local stakeholders interviewed. Indeed, associations significantly contribute to: **(i) community development and social cohesion**, as they strengthen social connections between inhabitants (especially in rural areas, as they often are the only actors present in the most marginal territories), sometimes through the organization of cultural events that promote local traditions and culture; **(ii) economic development**, as they contribute to local economy by promoting local products and producers; **(iii) advocacy and representation**, especially for vulnerable people such as PWDs and their families. The significance of associations for the area is also evident from the high level of volunteer engagement within them: despite a 15.7% decrease in active volunteers – as reported by ISTAT data of the Permanent Census of Non-Profit Institutions – between 2015 and 2021 within Italian non-profit organizations, the Province of Trento still boasts a robust and well-established network of associations. Remarkably, **about one in five residents of Trentino is involved in volunteer work**.

Associations are then followed by **cooperatives** (both social and other than social), which are 451 and employ a total of 22,774 people. The majority of social cooperatives are active in the Human health and social work activities (89 out of 120, i.e., 74.16%), while cooperatives other than social are mainly active in the Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycle sector (95 out of 331, i.e., 28.70%), followed by Manufacturing (44, i.e., 13.29%). However, it is important to note that data presented in both Table 14 and 15 do not include SEOs (including cooperatives) that are active in the agricultural sector. **Agricultural cooperatives** are particularly prominent in Trentino, playing a crucial role in sub-sectors such as viticulture, dairy, fruit production, and forestry. These cooperatives enable small farmers to pool resources, achieve economies of scale, improve product quality, and access broader markets. They also contribute to sustainable agricultural practices and rural development. According to 2024 data released by the Federazione Trentina delle Cooperative (FTC), agricultural cooperatives that are members of FTC are 79, distributed in sub-sectors as follows:

- fruit and vegetables: 27;
- winegrowing: 16;
- dairy: 16;
- livestock breeding: 2;
- services: 18.

They employ 2,967 people and produce more than 720 million kilograms of products in their 53,771 cultivated and grazing hectares. Lastly, their turnover in 2024 amounts to EUR 1 395 million.

Besides agricultural cooperatives, important types of cooperatives are:

- **Consumer cooperatives:** they provide essential goods and services to their members, often at lower prices and with better terms than private retailers do. The Coop Trentino network, part of the larger Coop Italia, is a notable example, offering groceries and other retail services to local communities. According to FTC data, in Trentino there are 364 sale points, which are

located in 152 municipalities (out of a total of 166 municipalities). They count over 125,000 members and employ almost 2,000 persons;

- **Cooperative credit unions:** they provide financial services including savings, loans, and financial advice to individuals and small businesses. An example of these cooperatives is *Casse Rurali*. According to FTC data, 131,000 people are members of the 11 territory banks, which offer a widespread network of 282 branches, managed by 2,000 employees. These institutions support local economic activities, foster financial inclusion, and promote responsible lending practices. Moreover, they support voluntary work, schools, culture and sports and recreational activities – as shown in Box 4;

Housing and Social cooperatives: they mainly deliver social services, such as healthcare, education, and support for vulnerable populations. They play a key role in addressing social needs, creating job opportunities for disadvantaged groups, and enhancing social cohesion. In 2024, the housing cooperatives associated with FTC are 18 and the social cooperatives are 90.

Box 4 FTC Coworking spaces in the Autonomous Province of Trento

Once disused places, now regenerated and returned to the community, Trentino Federation of Cooperatives (*Federazione Trentina della Cooperazione, FTC*) coworking spaces offer local residents and visitors the opportunity to work close to home or their holiday destination. These spaces cater to freelancers, employees, companies and tourists to offer spaces that are both cosy and flexible. Each hub is equipped with fast and reliable connection, meeting rooms, and offices.

There are currently six active hubs in Trentino, located in different municipalities of the province:

Figure 9 Map of FTC coworking spaces in Trentino

The hubs are located in central locations, squares and main streets of towns, close to work contexts and places for socialising. In the hubs, users have the opportunity to network and create new opportunities and collaborations with other professionals.

The network of FTC coworking spaces plays a fundamental strategic role in the realisation of multifunctional community spaces, as it is already part of a consolidated territorial network. For instance, some *Casse Rurali* (Trentino cooperative credit banks) promote the use of coworking spaces as community hubs open to the entire population.

One of the main strengths of coworking spaces relies on the successful collaboration between actors: besides FTC, multiple actors of the territory cooperated for the realisation of these coworking spaces, e.g., Casse Rurali, Impact Hub Trento, Trentino Social Tank, and So.L.E. cooperative.

Foundations are another important actor in the Trentino territory. According to ISTAT data, 96 foundations are active in the Autonomous Province of Trento, employing more than 500 people. For what concerns their sector of activity, foundations operate in the following sectors: Other sectors (not elsewhere classified); Arts, entertainment and recreation; Education and Human health and social work activities.

Also significant is the presence of SEOs registered under **other legal forms** than the ones previously mentioned, i.e., mutual aid societies; social enterprises with a legal form other than a cooperative; church bodies; and amateur sports clubs. Indeed, together they represent 7.8% of the SEOs in Trentino.

Table 18 Main sector of activity of Social Economy Organisations in the Autonomous Province of Trento

Main sector of activity (NACE codes)*	Associations	Cooperatives (other than social)	Social cooperatives	Foundations	Other legal forms	Total
B: Mining and quarrying	-	1	-	-	-	1
C: Manufacturing	-	44	2	-	-	46
D: Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	-	3	-	-	-	3
E: Water supply; sewerage; waste management and remediation activities	-	2	-	-	-	2
F: Construction	-	36	-	-	-	36
G: Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	-	95	1	-	-	96
H: Transporting and storage	-	14	-	-	-	14
I: Accommodation and food service activities	-	5	9	-	-	14
J: Information and communication	-	14	-	-	-	14
K: Financial and insurance activities	-	19	-	-	-	19
L: Real estate activities	-	8	1	-	-	9
M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	-	16	-	-	-	16
N: Administrative and support service activities	-	36	9	-	-	45
P: Education	202	15	5	20	7	249
Q: Human health and social work activities	612	2	89	20	8	731
R: Arts, entertainment and recreation	4,256	15	1	24	146	4,442
S: Other services activities	-	6	3	-	-	9
Other**	657	-	-	32	367	1,056
Total***	5,727	331	120	96	528	6,802

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT data: *Asia Imprese, Asia Occupazione, Censimento Istituzioni non-profit (2021)*.

* Data on organisations active in agriculture are not available.

** Includes all activities falling under the category of membership organisations (ATECO 9499), excluded from the category of 'Other service activities' of ISTAT.

*** To make a match between the sectors in which co-operatives operate (defined with the classification ATECO), and the sectors in which other SEOs operate (defined through the International Classification on Non Profit Organisations - ICNPO), the ATECO-ICNPO correlation table by ISTAT (2015: pp.38) was used

Almost all interviewees believe that the SEOs play a fundamental role in the communities where they operate. The role of the social economy is particularly significant in rural regions, where both public and private for-profit entities lack the interest or resources to engage. In these areas, the social economy, and specifically cooperatives, ensure the provision of essential services (e.g., social and health services, consumer services, credit).

The Autonomous Province of Trento, as one interviewee notes,

*stands out [from other regions/territories in Italy] due to its **community-based, collaborative, and cooperative approach**. This is evident not only in cooperatives but also and especially in associations. It is one of the driving forces of Trentino.*

Some examples of the **specific contributions of the social economy** in rural areas that emerged from the interviews include:

- **Implementation of services and/or prevention activities** addressing specific issues and marginalization, such as dependency, educational poverty, and self-isolation;
- **Creation of job opportunities**, including for disadvantaged workers (particularly through social cooperatives focused on employment integration);
- **Development and strengthening of community relational networks** through social activities and initiatives involving citizens or segments of the population (especially through volunteer associations, which often collaborate with each other and with other social economy organizations like cooperatives);
- **Promotion of civic engagement** and responsibilities for the common good;
- **Rediscovery and enhancement of the region's cultural and artistic heritage**, including for tourism purposes;
- **Raising awareness and practicing democracy**, as SEOs have democratic governance and a strong focus on community and collective interests;
- **Planning and organizing sports and cultural initiatives** in the territory;
- **Advocacy and awareness-raising** on specific issues (e.g., on the rights of PWDs);
- **Creation of connections among various local actors**, as SEOs and cooperatives in particular can act as connectors and facilitate networking among different actors, both public and private, profit and non-profit. These connections are especially useful for addressing complex and multidimensional needs, which span various aspects of life. For example, this is the case for individuals with disabilities, who often face challenges not only in entering (and remaining in) the job market but also in socializing.

Nevertheless, SEOs also face several challenges – especially in rural areas – that affect their operations and sustainability. The following are the main difficulties identified through the interviews:

- **Recruiting staff** (especially in social cooperatives). This issue is not unique to rural areas, but these areas are more significantly affected. Lower wages in SEOs compared to public and for-profit entities are one of the reasons explaining the lack of attractiveness of the sector;
- **Lack of skills**, particularly in the digital area, among social economy personnel;
- **Legal constraints**, especially for social cooperatives involved in employment integration: despite the gradual expansion of the definition of disadvantaged workers at the European level, new social needs that deserve attention and for which social cooperatives could play a crucial role are excluded from the category of disadvantaged individuals under Law 381/1991;
- **Communicating** and making the specificities of SEOs understood, both to public entities (to ensure that the social value of their activities is recognized and rewarded) and to the broader public (citizens, traditional businesses, etc.);
- **Collaborating with public authorities**. Some public administrations struggle to recognize the specificities of the social economy and their role in analysing needs and designing solutions to unmet community needs. Especially in rural areas, the relationship between SEOs and public entities often goes through a single representative (usually the mayor or municipal assessor) from the public sector, leaving much to their discretion. Although the majority of interviewees view the relationship with public entities as positive and fruitful, there are criticisms. Indeed, the relationship between the social economy and public entities is not always equitable.
- **Networking** among social economy organizations, public entities, and traditional businesses. One of the tools created to encourage dialogue is the Solidarity Economy Districts (DES), i.e., civic, economic, and social experimentation laboratories supported by the Autonomous Province of Trento (see Box 5). However, even DES itself encounters difficulties in creating networks and communication processes among SEOs
- **Economic sustainability/stability**, as some SEOs – and especially Third sector organisations – rely mainly on public subsidies and contributions and struggle to achieve economic independence.

Box 5 Solidarity Economy Districts (DES)

The Solidarity Economy Districts (DES) are laboratories for civic, economic and social experimentation. They are realised through circuits capable of enhancing territorial resources according to criteria of equity, environmental and socio-economic sustainability.

DES can be activated for different aims, e.g., the creation of chains of consumption, production, distribution of goods and services, or work integration goals. The Province Council resolution n. 1949 of 27 November 2020 defines DES on the basis of ten characteristics:

1. Existence of a chain of financing, production, distribution and consumption of goods and services (following the principles of solidarity economy),

2. Plurality of actors (a minimum of 3 partners, of which at least one from the solidarity economy),
3. Designation of a representative,
4. Inclusive governance,
5. Rooting in the territory and social sustainability,
6. Focus on environmental sustainability,
7. Focus on the empowerment through work of disadvantaged people,
8. Accountability and evaluation of results,
9. Connecting the different DES and sharing good practices,
10. Accounting and evaluating results against stated objectives.

To be qualified as a Social DES, a District has also to satisfy three additional requirements:

1. Enlargement of the network to the social welfare, socio-medical or health area, depending on the users involved,
2. Compliance with minimum capacity requirements oriented towards economic sustainability,
3. Duty to involve disadvantaged persons.

DES comprise two categories:

- Thematic DES (e.g., DES on Social Agriculture, DES on Green Economy), characterised by a network focused on working on a common sector,
- Territorial DES (e.g., DES Vallagarina, DES Primiero, DES Fiemme e Fassa), characterised by different but converging initiatives on the same territory.

Figure 2 Map of DES in the Autonomous Province of Trento

Consolida (Consortium of Trentino social cooperatives), together with EURICSE and CBS Società Benefit (start-up focused on community building), had responded in spring 2021 to the call of the Secretariat of the Trentino Solidarity Economy by proposing an operational hypothesis for the experimentation of the first Solidarity Economy Centre. Its purpose is to inform, raise awareness and stimulate knowledge, interest and involvement of the Trentino economic fabric in solidarity economy by concretely orienting and accompanying interested realities to deepen the creation of DES. The activities of the Centre range from mapping and coaching to communication, with the general aim of supporting community awareness about DES and the solidarity economy.

To overcome these challenges, second-level organisations of SEOs play a crucial role in strengthening and supporting their members, representing their interests at provincial, regional, national and international levels. Moreover, second-level organisations provide support services (e.g., training, support in accessing funding and resources) to their members, facilitate networking, coordinate joint projects and help build synergies among SEOs. Table 19 below lists and describes the main second-level organisations in Trentino.

As an example of services provided by second-level organisations, since 2017 FTC has been developing inCooperazione, which is a platform that aims to reconnect cooperatives, members and the territory through the support of a digital platform and a series of projects aimed at local development. The projects are many and all aimed at generating value within the cooperative system and the local

community. They range from coworking spaces (see Box 4) to energy solutions such as etika, which also allows to support social initiatives.

Table 19 Main second-level organisations of the social economy in the Autonomous Province of Trento

Actor	Description
Centro Servizi per il Volontariato (CSV) Trentino https://www.volontariatotrentino.it/	With more than 170 affiliated associations, CSV Trentino organises, manages and provides support services to promote and strengthen the presence and role of volunteers in local Third Sector organisations.
Federazione Trentina delle Cooperative (FTC) https://www.cooperazionetrentina.it/	FTC represents the interest of its member cooperative, provides support and assistance and promotes the cooperative models in Trentino.
Federazione Trentina delle Pro Loco https://www.unplitrentino.it/	Representative organisation of the 213 Pro Loco (local voluntary associations aimed at promoting and developing the territory) active in Trentino and their about 20 000 volunteers.
Consolida https://www.consolida.it/	Consortium of 52 Trentino's social cooperatives. Its mission is to support and represent its members, enhancing their operational and managerial capacities and advocating on their behalf at various levels.

7. Conclusions and potential focus of MAP

Drawing on desk research and local stakeholder interviews, two specific Valley Communities have been selected as Multi Actor Platforms (MAPs): *Alta Valsugana and Bersntol* and *Vallagarina*.

The ***Alta Valsugana and Bersntol Valley Community*** is made up of 15 municipalities and its area extends over almost 360 km². In 2021, it counted 55,528 inhabitants, continuously growing since 2001³⁰. Its major town is Pergine Valsugana, which has been the set of the Kick-Off Meeting of the ESIRA project (09/07/2024).

The ***Vallagarina Valley Community*** is made up of 17 municipalities and its area is much bigger than the one of *Alta Valsugana and Bersntol* as it extends over 662 km². In 2021, it counted 91,619 persons, continuously growing since 1921. Its major town is Rovereto, which has been the set of the Kick-Off Meeting of the ESIRA project (08/07/2024).

Both territories present a significant presence of rural areas and share the **challenges** identified in the previous section of this report:

- demographic decline and progressive ageing;
- lack of/excessive distance from essential services (e.g., education, socio-health and cultural services);
- reduced access to education and lower quality of the educational offer;
- lack of cultural initiatives and facilities;
- limited access to infrastructures, e.g., ultra-wideband connectivity and mobility infrastructures;
- lack of employment opportunities and lower quality of the employment offer.

As already emphasized, the geographic isolation and low population density of the rural areas in both Valley Communities present significant challenges for the provision of essential services, which economic sustainability is constantly under pressure. Consequently, this scarcity of services renders these areas less habitable, particularly for families with children and elderly residents, **creating a cycle that perpetuates the underdevelopment of these areas and hinders the overall quality of life of their inhabitants.**

At the same time, both territories can rely on **valuable resources**, including the SEOs that already operate in these areas, albeit in varying capacities. In the preceding pages, we have endeavoured to highlight their tangible contributions through the description of specific projects (e.g., the C.O.P.E project, see Box 3), initiatives (e.g., co-working spaces, see Box 4), and innovative actions (e.g., consumer cooperatives as services of general economic interest, see Box 2).

³⁰ Data on the population and area of the *Alta Valsugana and Bersntol* and *Vallagarina* Communities are from the Statistical Yearbook of ISPAT: [https://statweb.provincia.tn.it/annuario/\(S\(zm4t4w55u0bqfwfcej4mofvx\)\)/tavola.aspx?id=1.1](https://statweb.provincia.tn.it/annuario/(S(zm4t4w55u0bqfwfcej4mofvx))/tavola.aspx?id=1.1)

To ensure the success of the ESIRA project, we believe **it is essential to leverage the resources of the territories**, including existing projects, accumulated expertise, established networks, and already activated economies.

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8. Regional overview: Abruzzo

8.1 The main characteristics of the territory

Abruzzo is a region located in central-southern Italy, and it is bordered by the Regions of Molise, Lazio and Marche. To the west, it is dominated by Apennine Mountains and to the east it is washed by the Adriatic Sea. Abruzzo covers an area of 10,830 km², comprising 305 municipalities.

Figure 3 Map of Abruzzo Region

Here is an overview of the Abruzzo administrative structure:

- a. Regional level: The region has its own regional council (*Consiglio Regionale*) and regional government (*Giunta Regionale*). The Regional Council and most of the departments of the Regional Government are located in the capital city, L'Aquila.
- b. Provincial Level: Abruzzo is divided in four Provinces: L'Aquila, Pescara, Teramo and Chieti. Every Province has a provincial council (*Consiglio Provinciale*) responsible for legislative functions and a provincial government (*Giunta Provinciale*), responsible for executive duties.

Figure 4 Map of Abruzzo

- c. Municipalities: Every province is divided into municipalities (Comuni), which are the smallest administrative units. These municipalities are responsible for local governance and public services.

Table 20 Abruzzo Provinces: Area and municipalities

Province	Municipalities	Area (km ²)
L'Aquila	108	5,047
Chieti	104	2,599
Teramo	47	1,954
Pescara	46	1,230

8.2 Geographic and historical aspects

Abruzzo is a predominantly mountainous region. Indeed, its territory is **65% mountainous**, hosting the highest peaks of the Apennines, such as Corno Grande (2912 m). The region is naturally divided into two macro areas, separated by the Majella and Gran Sasso mountain ranges: the inland area, which traces the province of L'Aquila, is formed by the sub-regions of the Aterno Valley (Alto Aterno, Conca Aquilana, Valle Subequana), Altopiano di Navelli, Valle del Tirino, Marsica, Conca Peligna, Altipiani maggiori d'Abruzzo and Alto Sangro, squeezed between the peaks of the various mountains of the Abruzzo Apennines.

Abruzzo is also distinguished by a **long coastline**, which extends for about 130 km, bordering the Adriatic Sea to the east. The coastal area, with the three provinces of Pescara, Chieti and Teramo, is mainly made up of an extensive hillside, over which the main valleys of the Pescara Valley, the Sangro Valley and the Tordino Valley spread out, and the narrow coastal plain.

According to the ISTAT report “The geography of inland areas in 2020 - Vast territories between potential and weaknesses”, two-thirds of the municipalities of Abruzzo (202 out of 305) are located in **inner areas** (ISTAT, 2022). The study identifies the municipalities with a joint offer of three types of service - health, education, and mobility - called Inter-municipal Poles and Poles and, based on the distance from the poles, classifies the other municipalities, into four bands with increasing relative distance: Belt, Intermediate, Peripheral, Outermost. The Intermediate, Peripheral, and Ultraperipheral municipalities represent the set of inner areas. In Abruzzo, five municipalities are classified as Poli, 98 as Belt, 89 as Intermediate, 80 as Peripheral, and 33 as Ultraperipheral. Of the total of 10,831 square kilometres of the Abruzzo territory, 6,836 concern the internal areas. Over 2,400 km² fell in inner areas classified as protected areas (out of a regional total of protected areas equal to 3,052 km) and 2,924 kilometres of internal areas that fall within the Natura 2000 network, a European Union-wide initiative aimed at conserving biodiversity by protecting natural habitats, wild fauna, and flora.

Abruzzo is renowned for its extensive and well-preserved **natural parks**, which are a significant aspect of its territorial system and contribute greatly to its environmental landscape

The region boasts three national parks—Abruzzo, Lazio and Molise National Park, Gran Sasso and Monti della Laga National Park, and Majella National Park—along with one regional park, the Sirente-Velino Regional Natural Park. Additionally, there are 38 protected areas, including oases, regional reserves, and state reserves. Overall, 36.3% of the region’s territory is safeguarded for environmental conservation. This area hosts 75% of Europe’s animal species and is home to rare wildlife such as the golden eagle, the Abruzzo wolf, the Abruzzo chamois, and the Marsican bear.

The region also features the Torre del Cerrano Marine Protected Area, Abruzzo’s only marine reserve. Established in 2010, it spans approximately 37 km² and preserves a unique coastal ecosystem, including one of the last surviving dune environments on a sandy shoreline in the region.

The national and regional parks of Abruzzo are not only important for conservation but also for local economies. They attract tourists from all over the world, who support local businesses and create job opportunities.

In Abruzzo, particularly within the L'Aquila and Chieti provinces, the two selected areas of the MAP, the most disadvantaged areas are generally the **inland, mountainous territories**. The majority of the municipalities (75%) are classified as Inner Areas according to the Italian National Strategy for Inner Areas.

L'Aquila Province is largely characterized by the presence of the Apennines, and it includes extensive areas of the Gran Sasso and Monti della Laga National Park and the Abruzzo, Lazio, and Molise National Park. It contains many small, isolated communities in the mountainous region.

Chieti Province features inland hilly and mountainous areas, with the western part including sections of the Majella National Park. Additionally, some municipalities bordering other regions, such as Molise, face challenges related to their peripheral location.

The climate in Abruzzo is strongly influenced by the presence of the central Apennines. While the coastal areas have a **Mediterranean-type climate** with hot, dry summers and mild, rainy winters, the hillside area has **sublittoral climatic characteristics** with temperatures that gradually decrease with altitude and rainfall that increases with altitude.

Protected natural areas, inland and coastal, are home to a rich animal and plant biodiversity. The region is frequently referred to as "the **greenest region in Europe**" because of its substantial proportion of protected natural areas.

Concerning Abruzzo's history, it reflects its resilience and adaptability. In the ancient period, it was home to Italic tribes like the Vestini and Marsi, later integrated into the Roman Empire, contributing to its culture and economy.

During the Middle Ages, Abruzzo was part of the Kingdom of Naples, with L'Aquila and Chieti emerging as key centres. L'Aquila, founded in the 13th century, became a hub for trade and wool production, enjoying autonomy under the protection of the Neapolitan kingdom. Chieti, one of Italy's oldest cities, was a cultural and administrative centre, known for its religious significance and strategic location.

In the 19th century, a period marked by social and economic challenges like poverty and emigration, Abruzzo joined unified Italy. The 20th century brought devastation from World War II, requiring significant reconstruction. Post-war investment in infrastructure and industry (especially in the Chieti province) spurred economic growth, while L'Aquila became a centre for education with its university's establishment in 1952.

Throughout the latter half of the 20th century, both L'Aquila and Chieti provinces faced the challenge of balancing industrial growth with the preservation of their rich cultural and natural heritage. The 1970s and 1980s saw continued economic diversification. In L'Aquila, the service and cultural sectors expanded, as well as small and medium enterprises. Meanwhile, Chieti continued to build on its industrial base, while also promoting tourism in areas like the Trabocchi Coast and historical centres. However, the 2009 L'Aquila earthquake caused widespread destruction, triggering a complex reconstruction effort focused on rebuilding infrastructure, historical sites, and community resilience.

8.3 Demography

As of 01/01/2023, Abruzzo has a total population of **1,272,627 inhabitants**³¹. L'Aquila, the region's capital, has a population of 69,900. However, the most populous city is Pescara, on the coast, with 119,500 inhabitants, followed by Teramo with 53,000 inhabitants and Chieti with 50,000.

The **demographic contraction** detected at the national level, particularly in the southern regions, also affected the Abruzzese population, which declined by 3.8% between 2015 and 2022, dropping from

³¹ Data from ISTAT (2024). *Popolazione e famiglie*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

1.32 million to 1.28 million. This decrease was even more pronounced in the region's mountain municipalities, where the population fell by 6.2%, surpassing the national average for mountainous areas (Openpolis, 2024c). In 2022, Abruzzo experienced a positive migration balance (+5,434)³². However, the positive net migration balance was not sufficient to offset the natural population change, resulting in an overall decrease in the population (-3,323).

The region also faces challenges related to **ageing**, especially in rural and mountainous areas. As of 01/01/2023, the child population share (under 18) constitutes 14.6% of the total population, reflecting a relatively young demographic segment, but the old age population share (65 and older) accounts for roughly 26.4%, indicating a significant ageing population³³.

Depopulation and ageing pose a threat to the sustainability of internal areas, in which one-third of the total population lives (i.e., 460,328 people), especially for small and remote villages (ANSA, 2022). To address this issue there are policies to support families and to attract people in the rural and mountainous areas, such as birth grants and new residents' incentives.

8.4 Economic situation

Abruzzo is categorized as a **Southern Italian economy**. In 2022, Abruzzo's GDP per capita was roughly EUR 27,100 (-18% compared to the national GDP per capita of EUR 33,000), reflecting challenges of Southern Italian economies³⁴.

Abruzzo economy is composite and presents different solid sectors. The Region is one of the prominent Regions for the development of the industrial sector. Major industrial sectors are **food, transport, telecommunications, textiles, pharmaceuticals and handicrafts**. The agribusiness sector, especially the pasta (De Cecco, Verrigni) and wine industries (Montepulciano d'Abruzzo, Trebbiano d'Abruzzo, Pecorino), is well-established and is a significant source of employment in the region. In addition, Abruzzo is the sixth region in Italy for olive oil production. During interviews, one local stakeholder emphasized the need to incentivize youth to work in the agricultural sector, as they are perceived as a source of innovation for the whole industry.

Abruzzo has a long tradition of **pastoralism** and nowadays sheep farming is an important part of the agricultural sector. Pastoralism was widely practised using the technique of transhumance, moving livestock towards the Roman countryside and the Tavoliere delle Puglie (in the South of Italy). Today, livestock farming techniques have evolved, with a preference for stationary breeding in sheepfolds. The region still maintains a significant herd of sheep, while cattle farming is becoming increasingly widespread.

³² Data from AdminStat (2024). *Mappe, analisi e statistiche sulla popolazione residente. Abruzzo.* <https://uqeo.urbistat.com/AdminStat/it/it/demografia/popolazione/abruzzo/13/2>

³³ Data from ISTAT (2024). *Popolazione e famiglie.* Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

³⁴ Data from EUROSTAT (2024). *Gross domestic product (GDP) at current market prices by NUTS 2 regions.* Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nama_10r_2qdp_custom_10121922/default/table?lang=en

Another important aspect of the region's economy is its well-preserved **artisanal tradition**, which has been passed down through generations. Abruzzo is known for its production of a wide range of handcrafted goods, including ceramics (Castelli), ironwork (Scanno), gold, lace, textiles, copper, musical instruments (Giulianova, Teramo), stone (Pennapiedimonte, Lettomanoppello, Pretoro), wood and wool.

Tourism plays a crucial role in the economy, providing numerous job opportunities. It is mainly focused on the region's natural beauty, particularly its national parks and nature reserves. The Majella, Gran Sasso, and Abruzzo National Parks attract thousands of visitors each year, drawn to the unspoiled wilderness, rare wildlife, and scenic landscapes. The region is also known for its winter tourism, with ski resorts like Roccaraso, Ovindoli and Campo Felice offering opportunities for skiing, snowboarding, and other winter sports. The coastline, particularly along the Trabocchi Coast, draws tourists during summer and offers well-equipped beach establishments for visitors. In addition to nature-based tourism, the region is rich in historical and cultural landmarks, including medieval castles, churches, and monuments in cities like L'Aquila, Sulmona, and Chieti. Abruzzo also boasts a number of picturesque villages, with 26 towns officially recognized as some of the most beautiful in Italy (Borghi più belli d'Italia).

However, numerous local stakeholders interviewed identified significant challenges associated with overtourism in coastal regions, including peak-season overpopulation and escalating prices in tourist hotspots. Conversely, they highlighted the underutilization of inland areas' tourism potential, particularly the social and natural heritage of mountainous regions. Several stakeholders also emphasized the insufficient infrastructure and limited tourism offerings in these areas, which discourage extended stays by visitors.

Regarding the two provinces selected for the MAP, namely L'Aquila and Chieti, **L'Aquila** revolves around the service and industrial sectors, as well as the presence of research centres and universities. The economic and urban development has been significantly impacted by the reconstruction efforts following the 2009 earthquake. **Chieti** has a strong industrial presence, particularly in the automotive sector in Val di Sangro. It is also prominent in the agri-food and textile sectors. The province is known for its tourism, with destinations such as the Trabocchi Coast (Costa dei Trabocchi), historical centres like Vasto and Lanciano, and the Majella National Park.

The **employment rate** in Abruzzo registered in the first quarter of 2021 is 61.6 % within the age group 15-64. This rate is consistent with the national one in the same age group (61.7%), reflecting a better situation of Abruzzo compared to other Southern Italian economies (Southern Italy's employment rate in the same period was 48.2%)³⁵.

³⁵ Data from ISTAT (2024). *Lavoro e Retribuzioni*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

8.5 Institutional setting

The availability of a stable and fast telematics **infrastructure** is one of the crucial elements on which the transition to digital is based. Notably, in 2019 a significant number of households still lacked Internet access at home, with 23.9% in Abruzzo and 23.8% in Italy (ISTAT, 2020).

In 2022 the Province of Teramo was the worst Province in the region in terms of FTTH (*Fiber to the Home*) coverage (35.5%) while Pescara was the most connected Province in the Region (68.1%) (ISTAT, 2023a).

Connecting internal areas is crucial to foster local development and create opportunities in remote areas. Digital Nomads Italian Association (*Associazione Italiana Nomadi Digitali*), in collaboration with *Officine del Gran Sasso* (a Recovery Plan funded project), hosted a workshop in Fiano Adriano (located in the Province of Teramo) to raise the awareness of stakeholders and local administrators on the importance of developing policies and projects capable of attracting remote workers, digital nomads and new temporary inhabitants³⁶.

During the interviews, local stakeholders pointed out that limited Internet and telecommunications network coverage hinders the possibility of taking advantage of the opportunities offered by digitization.

The **transportation network** of the Abruzzo region plays a fundamental role in connecting the area to the rest of Italy and beyond, facilitating both passenger and freight movement. The **highway system** is a crucial element of this infrastructure, with the A14 Autostrada Adriatica being one of the most important roads running along the entire coast of Abruzzo, linking the region's major cities to the rest of the country. Another significant route, the A24 Strada dei Parchi, was built in the 1970s and connects Rome with L'Aquila and Teramo. The highway passes through the Gran Sasso tunnel, where access is provided to the Gran Sasso National Laboratories. Apart from highways, the state road network in Abruzzo includes numerous important routes that, following the construction of the motorways, now primarily serve as tourist itineraries. These roads pass through some of the region's most scenic areas, including several national parks, allowing travellers to enjoy the natural beauty of Abruzzo.

When it comes to **maritime transport**, Abruzzo benefits from several important ports. The Porto di Ortona, the largest port in the region, handles substantial cargo traffic and is strategically positioned for maritime trade; Porto di Vasto, located in Punta Penna, is another important commercial port; Porto di Pescara, that offers extensive services and is an important hub for tourism. Lastly, the Porto di Giulianova is a smaller, fishing-oriented port, handling primarily the daily fish catch.

Furthermore, the Abruzzo region's **air transport** infrastructure is centred around the Pescara Airport, the only international airport in the region.

³⁶ For more information visit: <https://www.officinedelgransasso.it/events/nomadismo-digitale-una-grande-opportunita-di-sviluppo-demografico-economico-e-sociale-per-i-nostri-territori/>

The **railway network** in Abruzzo is another crucial component of the regional transport infrastructure. Extending over 524 km, the railways connect major cities and towns such as Pescara, Sulmona, and Teramo to other parts of Italy.

Despite numerous upgrades in recent years, there remains a **significant divide between the coastal areas**, where the modern Adriatic railway line serves major cities, **and the inland areas**, which are served by fewer, less competitive lines. Indeed, for 35.1% of municipalities in Abruzzo, railway and highway mobility infrastructures are inaccessible and distant (Openpolis, 2024a). Mobility challenges are particularly severe in depopulated mountainous areas like inner Abruzzo. Local stakeholders highlight inadequate infrastructure, such as roads and rail connections, which hinder daily travel and access to essential services, exacerbating depopulation. These regions are the most isolated from health, education, mobility, and economic hubs. Public debate recently intensified over the Rome-Pescara railway enhancement project, initially included in the national recovery plan but later excluded from funding during plan revisions.

However, these are **longstanding issues** within the region. The presence of transport infrastructures is a central aspect when discussing the marginalization or peripherality of local communities and territorial planning, aiming to improve citizens' quality of life and enhance business competitiveness. The debate is not solely about the presence of these infrastructures. The **ease of access** to mobility access points such as railway stations or highway exits, with reasonable travel times, is another critical issue directly linked to the former and affecting various other aspects, including depopulation and the region's economic competitiveness.

In Abruzzo, the delivery of **healthcare services** is primarily handled by local health authorities known as **Aziende Sanitarie Locali (ASLs)**, which oversee specific areas of the region, often corresponding to provincial boundaries. For instance, the province of Chieti is served by the ASL of Lanciano-Vasto-Chieti, while L'Aquila has its own ASL (Avezzano-Sulmona-L'Aquila). The other provinces, Teramo and Pescara, are managed by their respective ASLs.

One of the key components of healthcare in Abruzzo is the network of general practitioners (GPs) and paediatricians, who are contracted with the National Health Service (SSN) to provide essential primary care services. Medical continuity is ensured through the presence of *guardie mediche* (on-call doctors), who are responsible for providing emergency care outside of regular office hours.

Another critical aspect of the region's healthcare system is home-based care. Abruzzo has a relatively high demand for integrated home care services, with 1,989 cases per 100,000 inhabitants in 2019, above the national average (Openpolis, 2022b). These services are particularly focused on elderly patients, offering medical, nursing, and rehabilitative care.

The region also has a **well-developed network of healthcare facilities**. In 2019, 35.7% of healthcare facilities in Abruzzo were outpatient clinics and laboratories. Additionally, there are **85 residential care facilities and 16 semi-residential centres** in Abruzzo, most of which are publicly managed. The region has a high percentage of publicly managed territorial healthcare structures, such as mental health centres, dialysis centres, and family counselling centers (Openpolis, 2022b).

In terms of hospital care, Abruzzo is home to **17 public hospitals and 10 private accredited nursing homes**³⁷. The region's elderly population, particularly those over 80, represents a significant share of hospital admissions, and Chieti has the highest proportion of seniors in the region.

Looking more closely at the data (Table 22 and Table 23), the distribution in the two territories selected for the MAP highlights notable differences in healthcare infrastructure. **L'Aquila** hosts 10 healthcare facilities with a total of 1,027 hospital beds, underscoring its significance as a regional medical hub. However, the slightly lower number of beds compared to Chieti suggests a need to assess whether current resources can adequately meet local demand. **Chieti**, on the other hand, has fewer facilities, with 7 in total, but offers a slightly higher capacity of 1,121 beds, which may point to a more centralized or specialized service structure. These variations underline the importance of addressing potential disparities in access, availability, and specialization to ensure that healthcare provision is equitable and meets the needs of both territories effectively.

Overall, the Abruzzo healthcare system faces **challenges** in providing adequate services to its rural and mountainous areas, where access to healthcare can be more limited.

Regarding the **distribution of schools**, as of 2017, Italy offers an average of 24.7 nursery school spots per 100 children aged 0-2. In Abruzzo, **the coverage is about three percentage points lower than the national average**. Within the region, the provinces of Pescara and L'Aquila show even lower availability. The province of Chieti stands out with 2,227 spots for over 8,500 children, achieving a coverage rate of 26.1%, which exceeds both the national (24.7%) and regional (21.6%) averages. Teramo follows with a slightly lower rate of 22.9%, still above the regional average. Pescara (19.1%) and L'Aquila (17.4%) have the lowest rates in the region.

In the city of Chieti, with 277 nursery spots for around 1,000 children, the coverage reaches 28.7%, 2.6 points above the provincial average. High coverage levels are also observed in nearby municipalities and central areas of the province. However, 63% of municipalities in the province, predominantly in mountainous areas, lack nursery school services entirely.

A positive aspect concerns the **school dropout rate**: Abruzzo stands out with a percentage 6 points lower than the national average, at 8.8%. Among the provinces, only L'Aquila exceeds the regional average, with a dropout rate of 10.9%. The other provinces perform significantly better, with Pescara at 6%, Chieti at 4.9%, and Teramo at 7.5% (Regione Abruzzo – Assessorato Politiche Sociali, n.d.).

Moreover, the education system in Abruzzo features a variety of **universities, research centers, and institutions** that contribute to a rich academic environment in the region. In terms of educational attainment, Abruzzo ranked eighth in Italy in 2013, with 23.6% of individuals aged 30 to 34 holding a university degree. Among the main public universities, the "Gabriele d'Annunzio" University of Chieti and Pescara is the largest in terms of student enrolment, with 24,716 students as of 2017. The University of L'Aquila follows with 16,421 students in 2018, while the University of Teramo, which was established in 1993 after separating from the "Gabriele d'Annunzio" University, had 5,810 students in

³⁷ Key hospitals include the San Salvatore Hospital in L'Aquila, the Spirito Santo Hospital in Pescara, and the Mazzini Hospital in Teramo.

2017. The region is also home to various private universities, including the online University "Leonardo da Vinci" in Torrecchia Teatina, the University "Niccolò Cusano" in Pescara, the Medio-Adriatica University in Teramo, and the European University of Design in Pescara. In L'Aquila there is also the Gran Sasso Science Institute, an international PhD school and a centre for advanced studies in physics, mathematics, computer science and social sciences. The institute was established following the 2009 earthquake in L'Aquila and it was conceived as a tool for economic recovery, aimed at revitalizing the region by the Ministry of Economy and Finance, in collaboration with the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD).

The region is also notable for its **scientific and technological research**. There are several specialized research centers, such as the International Center for Relativistic Astrophysics in Pescara and the Gran Sasso National Laboratories, located under the Gran Sasso mountain. The University of L'Aquila hosts the operational headquarters of the Italian Society for Science and Engineering at its Roio campus, which is dedicated to research and scientific dissemination. Additionally, L'Aquila is home to a center for sustainable transport and mobility within the university's Department of Engineering.

Finally, Abruzzo boasts several prestigious arts and music institutions, such as the State Conservatory "Gaetano Braga" in Teramo, the Luisa D'Annunzio Conservatory in Pescara, the Alfredo Casella Conservatory in L'Aquila, and the Academy of Fine Arts in L'Aquila, providing a diverse range of academic opportunities.

The three following tables present selected indicators for the Healthcare and Educational services respectively for the Abruzzo Region (Table 21), the Chieti province (Table 22) and the L'Aquila province (Table 23).

Table 21 Healthcare & Educational services in Abruzzo. Selected indicators.

Selected indicators	Abs./Rel. No.	Year of reference
Number of schools ^a , of which:	1,328	S.Y. 2021/2022
<i>Nursery schools</i>	556	
<i>Primary schools</i>	401	
<i>Lower secondary schools</i>	218	
<i>Upper secondary school</i>	153	
Pupils enrolled in early childhood education, of which:	31,184	S.Y. 2020/2021 - 2021/2022
<i>0-3 years^b</i>	2,317	S.Y. 2020/2021
<i>3-6 years^c</i>	28,867	S.Y. 2021/2022
Enrolment Ratio in Tertiary Education ^{1,d}	55.8%	2022
Number of healthcare facilities ^e	27	2021
Available beds in hospitals ^{2,e}	4,210	2021

Sources:

- a) Data aggregated from ISTAT (2024). Istruzione e Formazione. Scuole. <http://dati.istat.it/>
- b) Regione Abruzzo (2022). Nidi e servizi educativi per la prima infanzia. Regione Abruzzo. https://statistica.regione.abruzzo.it/sites/default/files/Aree/Popolazione_Lavoro_Societa/News/Servizi%20per%20l%27infanzia%20in%20Abruzzo%20-%202020.pdf
- c) Data from ISTAT (2024). Istruzione e Formazione. Scuole. <http://dati.istat.it/>
- d) ISTAT (2023). Annuario Statistico Italiano 2023. ISTAT. https://www.istat.it/storage/ASI/2023/ASI_2023.pdf

e) Data from ISTAT (2024). *Salute e sanità. Servizi sanitari e loro ricorso. Istituti di cura.*
<http://dati.istat.it/>

Notes:

1. The percentage of young adults aged 19-25 who are enrolled in university and residing within the same region. Data refers to 01/01/2022.
2. Beds in general inpatient care.

Table 22 Healthcare & Educational services in the Chieti province. Selected indicators.

Selected indicators	Abs./Rel. No.	Year of reference
Number of schools, of which:	n/a	
Nursery schools	n/a	
Primary schools	n/a	-
Lower secondary schools	n/a	
Upper secondary school	n/a	
Pupils enrolled in early childhood education, of which:	766 ¹	S.Y. 2020/2021
0-3 years ^a	766	S.Y. 2020/2021
3-6 years	n/a	-
Enrolment Ratio in Tertiary Education	n/a	-
Number of healthcare facilities ^b	7	2021
Available beds in hospitals ^b	1,121	2021

Sources:

- a) Regione Abruzzo (2022). *Nidi e servizi educativi per la prima infanzia. Regione Abruzzo.*
https://statistica.regione.abruzzo.it/sites/default/files/Aree/Popolazione_Lavoro_Societa/News/Servizi%20per%20l%27infanzia%20in%20Abruzzo%20-%202020.pdf
- b) Data aggregated from ISTAT (2024). *Salute e sanità. Servizi sanitari e loro ricorso. Istituti di cura.*
<http://dati.istat.it/>

Notes:

1. Data on pupils from 3 to 6 years old are not available therefore this figure may underestimate the total number of pupils enrolled in early childhood education in the area.

Table 23 Healthcare & Educational services in the L'Aquila province. Selected indicators

Selected indicators	Abs./Rel. No.	Year of reference
Number of schools, of which:	n/a	
Nursery schools	n/a	
Primary schools	n/a	-
Lower secondary schools	n/a	
Upper secondary school	n/a	
Pupils enrolled in early childhood education, of which:	306 ¹	S.Y. 2020/2021
0-3 years ^a	306	S.Y. 2020/2021
3-6 years	n/a	-
Enrolment Ratio in Tertiary Education	n/a	-
Number of healthcare facilities ^b	10	2021
Available beds in hospitals ^b	1,027	2021

Sources:

- a) Regione Abruzzo (2022). *Nidi e servizi educativi per la prima infanzia. Regione Abruzzo.*
https://statistica.regione.abruzzo.it/sites/default/files/Aree/Popolazione_Lavoro_Societa/News/Servizi%20per%20l%27infanzia%20in%20Abruzzo%20-%202020.pdf
- b) Data aggregated from ISTAT (2024). *Salute e sanità. Servizi sanitari e loro ricorso. Istituti di cura.*
<http://dati.istat.it/>

Notes:

1. Data on pupils from 3 to 6 years old are not available therefore this figure may underestimate the total number of pupils enrolled in early childhood education in the area.

8.6 Local policies and instruments

Abruzzo, like other regions in Italy, benefits from several national and European strategies aimed at fostering local development, particularly in rural areas:

- Abruzzo participates in the **National Strategy for Inner Areas** (*Strategia Nazionale per le Aree Interne* - SNAI). This strategy is designed to address the lack of necessary knowledge for effective policymaking in rural, non-core areas. In Abruzzo, 7 areas have been identified (5 in the first programming, to which two were added in the new 2021-27 programming): Basso Sangro Trigno (BST); Gran Sasso – Valle Subequana (GSVS); Valle del Giovenco – Valle Roveto (VGVR); Alto Aterno – Gran Sasso Laga (AAGSL); Valfino – Vestina (VFVE); Piana del Cavaliere – Alto Liri (PCAL); Valle del Sagittario e dell’Alto Sangro (VSAS) (Figure 13)
- Abruzzo implements measures from the **National Rural Development Program** (*Programma di Sviluppo Rurale Nazionale* - PSRN)³⁸. Abruzzo Rural Development Program 2014-2020 is one of the most important tools of the new Common Agricultural Policy (PAC) to support the growth of agriculture, forestry and rural areas in Abruzzo, focusing on sustainable, inclusive and smart growth.
- Abruzzo benefits from the **European Structural and Investment Funds** (ESIF), particularly through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and the European Social Fund (ESF), which support various regional development projects.
- The **National Fund for Rural Development** provides financial support to rural development projects in the areas of tourism, agriculture, entrepreneurship, services and environmental protection in the inland territories of the Region.
- Abruzzo participates in the **LEADER Programme**, with eight Local Action Groups (LAGs) operating in the region (Box. 2).

³⁸ PSRN is co-financed by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 13 NSIA areas for the period 2021-27

Source: Regione Abruzzo, <https://www.regione.abruzzo.it/content/aree-interne-ciclo-snai-2021-2027>

Box 6 Local Action Groups in Abruzzo

In Abruzzo there are **eight Local Action Groups (LAGs)**, which cover most of the region.

Figure 14 Map of Local Action Groups in Abruzzo

- **LAG Terreverdì Teramane** covers an area of 568.9 km² in the Province of Teramo. It comprises 16 inland municipalities and the rural area of 7 coastal municipalities. The territory shows an overall homogeneity in terms of both its physical-geographical and historical-cultural profile and its economic and social dynamics.

- **LAG Terre d’Abruzzo** covers an area of 1,373.4 km² in the Province of Teramo, comprising 26 municipalities. The LAG focus on the valorisation of local gastronomic heritage and on the creation of a network for actors in the tourism sector.
- **LAG Gran Sasso Velino** covers an area of 2,415.1 km² in the northern part of the Province of L’Aquila. Almost the entire territory contains areas of undoubted naturalistic value that represent a fundamental resource for local development.
- **LAG Terre Pescara** covers an area of 1,172.4 km² in the Province of Pescara, comprising 44 municipalities. It hosts part of the *Gran Sasso d’Italia* and *Majella* mountain groups, which constitute a naturalistic resource of considerable attractiveness. The area is characterized by extensive forests that represent a resource of great value. The territory comprised between the mountainous area and the shore is devoted to agriculture. This LAG aims to enhance the food and wine heritage of the area by offering support and assistance to operators through a network of services.
- **LAG Marsica** covers an area of 1,342.9 km² in the Province of L’Aquila, comprising 27 municipalities. The LAG focuses on the theme of tourism, aiming to transform a currently limited offer, characterized by strong seasonality and short stays, into a form of tourism centred on outdoor activities. This transition is supported by the development of local food production systems. Through these processes, the LAG seeks to promote social inclusion by involving disadvantaged individuals.
- **LAG Abruzzo Italico – Alto Sangro** covers an area of 1,330.7 km² in the Province of L’Aquila. It comprises areas of great tourist and naturalistic value such as Majella National Park and Abruzzo, Lazio and Molise National Park.
- **LAG Maiella Verde** covers an area of 1,944.5 km² in the Province of Chieti, comprising 81 municipalities. The territory comprises Majella National Park and five Natural Reserves. The LAG focuses on enhancing local services and in promoting a more bio-diverse agribusiness sector.
- **LAG Costa dei Trabocchi** covers an area of 492.5 km² in the Province of Chieti comprising 17 municipalities. The LAG focuses on promoting the local agribusiness sector and improving the cultural, tourist and recreational offer.

Despite the existence of various strategies aimed at social inclusion, local stakeholders raise numerous critical points regarding the effectiveness of actions to fight social exclusion. From the interviews, it emerged a substantial **lack of resources** and a severe issue derived from their **misallocation**. Many respondents underlined a severe deficit in project planning capabilities by both private and public actors, especially in small municipalities.

Local stakeholders highlighted a substantial difficulty of social economy actors in **networking** to increase the effectiveness of actions. They also underline in many cases a **failure of the public authority to recognise the importance of social economy**. Moreover, many stakeholders underline a substantial **absence of social economy actors in peripheral and ultra-peripheral municipalities**. In some cases, where these actors exist, they are incapable to satisfy people's needs. Examples of key strategies and actors to promote social inclusion in rural areas are:

- **Social Cooperatives**, which play a crucial role in providing social services, creating job opportunities for disadvantaged groups, and fostering social integration in rural areas. An interesting case is *FormaTalenti* Cooperative, which partner of *RURA* project³⁹. The project aims to increase the capacity of participating youth workers and partner organisations to promote quality initiatives for the benefit of young people living in rural settings.
- **Third Sector and Volunteering Initiatives**, which include projects that provide social care, educational support, and create opportunities and activities for the youth in rural areas. For example, different local stakeholders underline the role of Pro Loco⁴⁰ as the only point of aggregation and social life in small municipalities.
- **Health and Social Care Initiatives**, such as the expansion of telemedicine services to provide healthcare in remote areas, reducing the need for travel and improving access to medical consultations.
- **Youth policies**, such as Abruzzo Giovani, a regional policy with the scope of supporting the transition from supporting the transition from school to work, with a particular focus on NEETs, and preventing the risk of social exclusion for young people.
- **Migrants' integration policies**, national and EU-funded programs that support the social and occupational integration of migrants in rural areas.

³⁹ *RURA* is a project funded under the Erasmus+ Programme. For more information visit: <https://www.formatalenti.eu/progetti/>

⁴⁰ Pro Locos are local associations, created with the aim of promoting and developing the area in which they operate.

9. Vulnerability and social exclusion in the region

9.1 Social exclusion and poverty

In recent years, Abruzzo has faced significant socio-economic challenges, as evidenced by several indicators of poverty, social exclusion and employment. According to data collected by the Abruzzo Region, in 2021 27.7% of the population lived at risk of poverty or social exclusion, a figure significantly higher than the Italian national average of 20.1%. This figure includes several situations of hardship, including a 6.1% share of the regional population living in conditions of severe material deprivation, a figure that is higher than the national average, which stands at 5.9 % (Statistica Regione Abruzzo, 2023).

Another critical element is the working condition. In fact, in Abruzzo, 13.2% of people under 60 live in households with very low work intensity, a figure that exceeds the 11.7% recorded nationally (Statistica Regione Abruzzo, 2023). This phenomenon reflects structural difficulties in the regional labor market, which particularly affect young people and women. The high rate of youth unemployment, which affects the 15-24 age group, is one of the most pressing issues and highlights the urgency of active job placement policies (Statistica Regione Abruzzo, 2024). These challenges were exacerbated by a limited number of stable job opportunities and dependence on seasonal or precarious work, particularly in sectors such as tourism and agriculture. Moreover, women in Abruzzo experienced higher unemployment rates compared to men, underlining persistent gender inequalities in the labor market (Statistica Regione Abruzzo, 2024).

Given these challenges, welfare measures such as the Citizenship Income have provided significant economic support to many families in Abruzzo. In 2021, more than 25,000 households benefited from this tool, receiving an average of about €500 per month (Ministero del Lavoro e delle Politiche Sociali, 2021). However, despite the important impact of these transfers, there remains a clear need for more structured interventions to address the roots of poverty and social exclusion.

Data also emerge in the field of education that requires attention. Although Abruzzo has lower school dropout rates than the national average, some areas of the region, particularly rural and disadvantaged areas, continue to show criticality. The risk of early school dropout is related to both economic hardship and the lack of real job opportunities for young graduates. For this reason, investing in vocational education and training could be a key strategy for improving employment prospects and fostering social inclusion (Statistica Regione Abruzzo, 2024).

9.2 Disadvantaged groups

In the Abruzzo Region, different groups of the population may be regarded as vulnerable: NEETs, women, people with disabilities (PWDs), immigrants and the elderly. The sections below describe, for each of these categories, their main characteristics, the causes behind their vulnerability, how the vulnerability is affecting their life conditions and opportunities and the main challenges they face.

9.2.1 NEETs

Regarding the phenomenon of NEETs, the situation in the Abruzzo region is slightly less severe compared to the national level: in 2020 NEETs represented **20.7%** of the reference population, compared to 23.3% nationwide⁴¹. Among the female population, the percentage of NEETs was higher (22.9%) compared to the male population in the same age group (18.6%)⁴².

The Abruzzo Region is more affected by the phenomenon compared some Northern Regions. This figure is consistent with empirical results on determinants of NEETs condition, enlightening the higher risk of being a NEET for women and inhabitants of Southern Italy (Quintano et al., 2018).

In the interviews, most respondents underline a widespread lack of initiative and enthusiasm in the youth, especially in rural areas. A possible explanation of the phenomenon given by a respondent is the lack of activities outside formal education for young people.

In the Region, there are several instruments to combat youth inactivity, for example:

- **Garanzia Giovani:** as mentioned in the *Country overview* and Annex 1, *Garanzia Giovani* is a European initiative to offer training opportunities, internships and job placement assistance to young NEETs between 15 and 29.
- **Abruzzo Giovani:** a programme co-funded by the Abruzzo Region and the national Department for Youth Policies and Universal Civil Service (*Dipartimento per le Politiche Giovanili e il Servizio Civile Universale*). The programme aims to foster social inclusion in the young population, targeting, among others, young NEETs between 14 and 35. Specifically, the programme promotes the transition from school to work in the attempt to reduce the incidence of NEETs in the young population⁴³.

Furthermore, the Abruzzo region has outlined an ambitious agenda for youth policies in its **2022–2024 Regional Social Plan**. This framework focuses on enhancing social integration, combating school dropout rates, and reducing youth unemployment through targeted and innovative interventions. These policies are organized under the thematic axis “*Axis 6: Youth and Youth Guarantee*” and encompass a variety of programs and strategies aimed at supporting young people across multiple dimensions.

One of the cornerstones of these initiatives is the enhancement of day centres for the social integration of young people, established under the framework of Law 248/2006 on youth policies. Another key focus of the plan is fostering community services for the social inclusion of young people, particularly through initiatives like the *Youth Guarantee Program*. These services include the *Inclusive Spaces Project*, funded by the European Social Fund (ESF), which promotes collaboration between local health districts and third-sector organizations to create inclusive networks for youth. Additionally, regional

⁴¹ Data from ISTAT (2020). *Lavoro e retribuzioni*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

⁴² Data from ISTAT (2020). *Lavoro e retribuzioni*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

⁴³ For more information: <http://www.abruzzosociale.it/site/main/post/370>

projects such as *Officina delle idee*—which features experiential educational labs—aim to build a stronger connection between young people and their communities. By strengthening these services, the region seeks to address critical issues such as school dropout rates and youth unemployment, which remain persistent challenges.

Another significant intervention involves strengthening **dual education systems** and **job orientation services** to improve young people’s transition into the labour market. This includes integrating social and labour policies, promoting active employment measures, and fostering initiatives such as gender equality certification and support for women entrepreneurs. These efforts are bolstered by larger programs like *PNR M5C1 Policies for Work* and regional initiatives under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan. Projects focusing on lifelong learning, university scholarships, business creation, and job retention are also being prioritized.

One of the latest projects is the **Teenace project**, launched by the Municipality of Pescara, which aims to support NEET in the region. With a total budget of EUR 213,254, the project focuses on strengthening the transition from school to work and building a stable local network of stakeholders. It targets 40 NEET individuals: 10 graduates, who will serve as tutors, and 30 non-graduates, offering them personalized training and peer tutoring opportunities. The project includes data collection, social surveys, and mapping the specific needs of NEET youth to provide concrete support for their integration into the workforce.

9.2.2 Women

In 2023, there were **649,948 women** in Abruzzo, representing 51% of the total population⁴⁴. Datadisplay a positive state of female education in the area (e.g., the percentage of women with a bachelor, master or PhD degree⁴⁵, i.e., 24.3%, is higher compared to men, i.e., 18%)⁴⁶.

Conversely, a **gap in employment** persists. Women employed in the Abruzzo Region are considerably less than men (52.3% against 70.8%). The inactivity rate is higher for women (42.9%) than for men (24%)⁴⁷. Despite that, in 2022, there were around 214,000 female workers in Abruzzo, with nearly one-third being self-employed, including entrepreneurs and freelancers. This group plays a vital role in sustaining local economies, especially in peripheral areas, by investing in and operating businesses. In fact, Abruzzo ranks ninth in Italy for female self-employment (but first among southern regions), with 32.7%, and several inland communes report even higher female self-employment rates, such as Colledimacine and Montelapiano, both at 66.7%. In provincial capitals, Chieti has the highest female self-employment rate at 34.1% (Openpolis, 2024b).

In the **political arena**, a persistent gender gap is evident in the recent regional elections in Abruzzo. The newly elected regional council, consisting of 31 members, is predominantly male. The number of women in the new regional council has significantly decreased, dropping by 50% compared to the

⁴⁴ Data from ISTAT (2023). *Popolazione e famiglie*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

⁴⁵ Corresponding to ISCED 6-7.

⁴⁶ Data from ISTAT (2020). *Istruzione e formazione*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

⁴⁷ Data from ISTAT (2024). *Lavoro e Retribuzioni*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

previous assembly. While the outgoing council included six women out of 31 members, the current composition now includes only three women. This represents a sharp reduction in female representation, which was already quite limited.

Regarding the issue of **gender violence**, data show that the situation in Abruzzo is roughly consistent with the national context⁴⁸. Considering the age group from 16 to 70, in 2014 22.3% of the women had suffered forms of physical violence in their lifetime (in more than half of the cases the aggressor was a partner or a former partner) and 4.9% in the last 12 months. In the same year, 22.6% of the women reported having been victims of sexual violence in their lives. In roughly a third of the cases, the aggressor was a partner or a former partner. These data underline the severity of the issue of domestic violence⁴⁹.

During interviews, a local stakeholder indicated that the most vulnerable category of women is **unemployed women over the age of 40**, especially the poorly educated ones. This is motivated by the fact that the average age at which people have children has significantly increased, thus the ones who are willing to enter the labour market have to balance working time and childcare.

The Region of Abruzzo has long prioritized **gender equality** through systematic policies and laws that address women's empowerment. Key legal frameworks include:

- Regional Law No. 143/1995 supporting female entrepreneurship,
- Regional Law No. 26/2004 tackling mobbing and workplace stress,
- Regional Law No. 40/2005 coordinating city time policies,
- Regional Law No. 31/2006 promoting shelters for women victims of violence.

The primary goals of these initiatives have been to combat gender-based violence through the establishment of shelters and support services. In the 2017-2019 program, the Region also implemented **work-life balance measures** for women, especially those providing care for children, the elderly, or family members with disabilities.

For the 2022-2024 Social Plan, Abruzzo aims to integrate a **gender perspective** in all future policies, aligning with the European and National Gender Equality Strategies. This includes promoting gender equality in all sectors and addressing gender disparities exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Increased caregiving duties and the shift to remote work during the pandemic worsened existing inequalities, especially among women in precarious or autonomous work situations.

The region's future priorities include improving **public services for family care**, expanding childcare facilities, and enhancing gender equality within the family, including paid paternity leave. Measures will also include developing flexible work arrangements, encouraging women's participation in STEM fields, and combating gender stereotypes through education and public campaigns.

⁴⁸ Data from ISTAT (2014). *Giustizia e Sicurezza*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

⁴⁹ Data from ISTAT (2014). *Giustizia e Sicurezza*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

Abruzzo plans to address post-pandemic challenges by **increasing investment in welfare services**, particularly for the elderly and disabled, and promoting policies that enable women to balance family responsibilities with professional careers. Additionally, the region aims to provide targeted training for women who have left the workforce or face challenges due to economic crises.

These initiatives, aligned with national strategies, are crucial to reducing gender imbalances and fostering both social and economic development.

9.2.3 People with disabilities

In 2009 in Abruzzo, formally recognized PWDs were **13,652**. Abruzzo shows a higher presence of PWDs in both **primary and secondary schools** (3.9%) than the national average (3.3%), underlining a strength in promoting social inclusion through the school system in the Region (Regione Abruzzo, 2022).

Abruzzo exhibited a positive trend regarding **homecare services**. The region experienced a rise in the number of people benefiting from different kinds of homecare services and in the number of municipalities providing these (Assessorato Politiche Sociali, 2022). However, the expenses of municipalities for intervention and social services for PWDs remain lower than the national average (EUR 2,669 against EUR 3,212 in 2018). The major weakness is the expenses of municipalities for residential care facilities which is roughly half of the national average (EUR 6,227 against EUR 11,660).

The Abruzzo Region's **2022-2024 Regional Social Plan** (in Italian, *Piano Sociale Regionale – PSR*) aims to improve the quality of life, inclusion, and autonomy of people with disabilities through direct services, financial assistance, and innovative programs. The plan integrates health, social, and community services, leveraging regional, national, and European resources. Key initiatives include home and community care, semi-residential and residential programs, and social and professional inclusion efforts, such as health and social integration services and autonomy pathways. Innovative independent living programs, supported by the National Fund for Social Policies, are also included.

The PSR provides financial support for families and caregivers, including caregiver support budgets and subsidies for socioeconomic integration. It strengthens the role of caregivers and community networks by promoting proximity services and coordinated access to care. The plan emphasizes the integration of health and social services and the creation of inclusive spaces, such as day centres, community hubs, and housing solutions, to promote autonomy and participation. Third-sector organizations collaborate with public institutions to provide locally relevant services.

The PSR also includes initiatives funded by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan and React EU, focusing on autonomy and social inclusion. The main goals are to expand service access, reduce reliance on institutional care, and enhance opportunities for participation in education, employment, and community life, fostering a more inclusive society. By adopting a holistic and integrated approach, the PSR seeks to create meaningful and lasting change for people with disabilities in the region.

9.2.4 Immigrants

In 2022 there were **80,988 foreign residents** in Abruzzo, accounting for 6.3% of the total population of the Region and for 1.6% of total foreign residents in Italy⁵⁰. Among them, women were 42,730, accounting for 52.8% of the foreign residents' population in the Region.

In 2022, **Romanians** were the largest community, followed by Albanians (Openpolis, 2023)⁵¹. Together they represented 40.1% of the total foreign population in Abruzzo. Moroccans are the third foreign community by size.

As Table 24 shows, the distribution of foreign residents is **not homogeneous across Provinces**. More than half of the foreign resident population is located in the Provinces of Chieti (23.9%) and L'Aquila (28.3%).

Table 24 Foreign resident population in Abruzzo by Province

Province	N.	%
L'Aquila	22,957	28.3
Teramo	21,819	26.9
Pescara	16,825	20.8
Chieti	19,387	23.9
Abruzzo	80,988	100.0

Source: ISTAT (2024). *Popolazione e Famiglie*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.asp>. Reference Year: 2022

Interviews indicate that immigration policies do not sufficiently incentivize immigrants to settle down in the region. Respondents emphasize the need for more incentivizing immigration policies to face depopulation and the demand for labour, especially unskilled labour.

9.2.5 Elderly people

In 2023, residents of 65 years or older in the Abruzzo Region were **336,285**, of which 186,384 were female (i.e., 55.4% of the elderly population). Inhabitants in the age group of 65 years and over represent 26.4% of the population of the region, slightly more than the national context (24%)⁵².

As of 01/01/2022, the **ageing index** – i.e. the ratio of the percentage of the population over 65 to young people up to the age of 14 – stands at 207.3⁵³. In other words, for every 100 young people there are approximately 207 elderly people. This figure displays Abruzzo as an old region compared to the national context (Italy displayed an ageing index of 187.6 in the same year).

The Region of Abruzzo has developed **Active Ageing policies** in three key areas: (1) Active Ageing as an integrated, multidimensional intervention; (2) support for family caregivers; and (3) promoting the health of the elderly. The regional law LR 16/2016 focuses on valuing the elderly's role in society,

⁵⁰ Data re-elaborated from ISTAT (2014). *Popolazione e Famiglie*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

⁵¹ Openpolis (2023). *Scuola, sanità e mobilità: le politiche per l'inclusione degli stranieri in Abruzzo*. Openpolis. <https://www.openpolis.it/scuola-sanita-e-mobilita-le-politiche-per-linclusione-degli-stranieri-in-abruzzo/>

⁵² Data from ISTAT (2024). *Popolazione e famiglie*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

⁵³ Data elaborated from ISTAT (2024). *Popolazione e famiglie*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.aspx>

combating discrimination, and promoting their autonomy and well-being through various actions, including lifelong learning, social volunteering, and the use of new technologies. It also establishes a Regional Day for Active Ageing. In 2016, the law was funded with €50,000 through the Regional Social Fund (Cela, 2020).

The Regional Law 43/2016 recognizes and supports family caregivers, including those without familial ties to the person being cared for. It provides financial support, guidance, and access to services, along with promoting caregiver associations. The law also establishes a "Caregiver Day."

The Regional Prevention Plan includes initiatives to increase physical activity among people over 64, such as the "Cities for Walking and Health" project, which promotes accessible walking routes.

Figure 15 displays a constrictive pyramid (trapezoid-shaped) suggesting an ageing of the population.

Source: ISTAT (2024). *Popolazione e Famiglie*. Retrieved from <http://dati.istat.it/Index.asp>. Reference Year: 01/01/2022

From the analysis of the interviews, a need for sociality among the elderly in the most remote areas emerges. A respondent underlined the necessity to provide socialization spaces for the elderly in the most remote municipalities.

Concurrently, different respondents underlined a substantial difficulty in accessing services for the elderly in rural areas. **Technology** could address some of the constraints to service access. For example,

the Community-based Cooperative *Vivi Calascio* activated a health monitoring service through a smartwatch for the elderly living in the village of Calascio⁵⁴.

⁵⁴ For more information visit: <https://www.vivicalascio.com/progetto-anziani-calascio/>

10. Assets and potential in the region

10.1 Social Economy Organization in the Region

Social economy organizations (SEOs) are widespread in Abruzzo, playing a significant role in addressing social and economic challenges. Table 25 shows that associations are the prevalent organizational form, while most of the employees belong to cooperatives (social and other).

Associations are 7,379 (representing 82.1% of SEOs) and employ 1,917 workers. They play a crucial role in the local social fabric, especially in remote villages. Local stakeholders state that Pro Loco are the focal point of social life in small rural villages. However, they complain about a frequent lack of cooperation between these associations.

Cooperatives (both social and other than social) are 1,022 (338 are social cooperatives, representing 33% of total cooperatives), employing 15,188 workers. Particularly, social cooperatives only represent 3.8% of the SEOs in the Region, but they employ 37.1% of the sector.

Table 25 Social economy organisations in Abruzzo

Legal forms	Social Economy Organisations*		Employees**	
	N.	%	N.	%
Associations	7,370	82.1	1,917	9.9
Cooperatives (other than social cooperatives)	684	7.6	7,971	41.0
Social cooperatives	338	3.8	7,217	37.1
Foundations	151	1.7	1,496	7.7
Other legal forms***	434	4.8	838	4.3
Total	8,977	100.0	19,440	100.0

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT data: *Asia Imprese, Asia Occupazione, Censimento Istituzioni non-profit (2021)*.

* Data on organisations active in agriculture are not available. Thus, the figures reported in this table may underestimate the actual number of SEOs in Trentino.

** As of 31/12/2021 for all legal forms except for cooperatives (other than social cooperatives): annual average.

*** This category includes mutual aid societies; social enterprises with a legal form other than a cooperative; church bodies; and amateur sports clubs.

Regarding the main sectors of activity of SEOs, as shown in Table 26, the three main sectors are: arts, entertainment and recreation; health and social works activities; and education. While associations operate only in these three sectors, cooperatives (both social and other) are the form of organisation of social economy which are widespread the most across sectors (although the majority of social cooperatives, 53%, operate in human health and social work sector).

- **Social cooperatives:** play a crucial role in providing services and social inclusion opportunities to the most vulnerable categories.
- **Agricultural and fishery cooperatives:** including cooperatives for agricultural production, marketing, processing and transformation of agricultural products, supply services and

technical means, they offer numerous job opportunities both on the coast and in the internal areas of Abruzzo

- **Cooperative credit unions:** in the whole Region there are 74 bank tellers belonging to Cooperative banking group (*Gruppo bancario cooperativo*), which is constituted by 117 Cooperative credit unions in the national territory (GRUPPO BCC Iccrea, 2024)⁵⁵. They provide financial services including savings, loans, and financial advice to individuals and small businesses.
- **Housing cooperatives:** these cooperatives in Abruzzo are characterised by innovative programmes that tend to diversify their activities in order to make them capable of intervening in new market segments and housing services, thus responding to new needs of citizens. The founding principle is to organise housing needs in a mutualistic way to give their members access to housing at better than market conditions.
- **Health cooperatives:** these cooperatives are active players in health reorganisation processes in the territory.

Table 26 Main sector of activity of Social Economy Organisations in Abruzzo

Main sector of activity (NACE codes)*	Associations	Cooperatives (other than social)	Social cooperatives	Foundations	Other legal forms	Total
B: Mining and quarrying	-	-	-	-	-	0
C: Manufacturing	-	91	7	-	-	98
D: Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	-	2	-	-	-	2
E: Water supply; sewerage; waste management and remediation activities	-	5	6	-	-	11
F: Construction	-	101	1	-	-	102
G: Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	-	66	7	-	-	73
H: Transporting and storage	-	54	8	-	-	62
I: Accommodation and food service activities	-	47	14	-	-	61
J: Information and communication	-	51	5	-	-	56
K: Financial and insurance activities	-	28	-	-	-	28
L: Real estate activities	-	3	1	-	-	4
M: Professional, scientific and technical activities	-	44	3	-	-	47
N: Administrative and support service activities	-	122	52	-	-	174
P: Education	94	9	26	38	21	188
Q: Human health and social work activities	822	14	181	33	18	1,068
R: Arts, entertainment and recreation	5,417	19	5	50	237	5,728
S: Other services activities	-	28	22	-	-	50
Other**	1,037	-	--	30	158	1,225
Total***	7,370	684	338	151	434	8,977

Source: own elaboration based on ISTAT data: *Asia Imprese, Asia Occupazione, Censimento Istituzioni non-profit (2021)*.

⁵⁵ Data retrieved from the GRUPPO BCC Iccrea website: <https://www.gruppobcciccrea.it/Pagine/ChiSiamo/Le-BCC.aspx#!>

* Data on organisations active in agriculture are not available.

** Includes all activities falling under the category of membership organisations (ATECO 9499), excluded from the category of 'Other service activities' of ISTAT.

*** To make a match between the sectors in which co-operatives operate (defined with the classification ATECO), and the sectors in which other SEOs operate (defined through the International Classification on Non-Profit Organisations - ICNPO), the ATECO-ICNPO correlation table by ISTAT (2015: pp.38) was used.

Overall, Abruzzo displays a positive trend in the development of social economy in the Region. The **value added** of the cooperative system in the Region experienced a substantial rise in the period 2020-2021 (+14.4%) compared to the national context (+9.4%) (Eurisce, 2003).

One of the most prominent actors of the social economy in the region are Community-based Cooperatives, which were created in Abruzzo through the Regional Law 25/2015. In the next paragraph, some features of Community-based Cooperatives will be presented.

10.2 Community-based Cooperatives

Community-based cooperatives (CBCs) are a model of social innovation where citizens are producers and users of goods and services, acting both as an entrepreneur and an enterprise. They are economic entities deeply rooted in specific places created by the people who live and work there to produce goods and services in various sectors to enhance the economic and social well-being of the community. Hence, CBCs are not defined by the type of traditional cooperative (social, worker, users, production, etc.) but instead by the purpose of enhancing the community. In Abruzzo, CBCs are regulated by the Regional Law no. 25/15⁵⁶.

One village in ten in Abruzzo has focused on CBCs as an economic and social tool for a better present and future. Out of 305 municipalities in the Region, 32 have established CBCs, which are now part of the *BorghilN* network⁵⁷. Most of them are located in the most vulnerable rural areas, where CBCs are experimenting with a new form of territorial planning, starting from the needs of the communities to which they refer, by triggering bottom-up transformative processes that are a virtuous example of social innovation, understood as the ability to give a sustainable and non-extractive collective response to rooted social needs. As shown in Table 27, most of them are located in the Provinces of L'Aquila and Chieti, the two MAPs territories.

Table 27 Community-based Cooperatives in Abruzzo by Province

Province	Community-based Cooperatives
L'Aquila	15
Chieti	12
Teramo	3
Pescara	2
Abruzzo	32

Source: BCC Abruzzi e Molise (2021). *Cooperative di comunità: l'Abruzzo vuole ripartire dal basso*. BCC Abruzzi e Molise. <https://www.bccabruzzimolise.it/news/cooperative-di-comunita-l-abruzzo-vuole-ripartire-dal-basso/>

⁵⁶ Provincial Law no. 25 of 8 October 2015. *Community-based Cooperatives Legal Framework (Disciplina sulle cooperative di comunità)*: http://www2.consiglio.regione.abruzzo.it/leggi_tv/abruzzo_lr/2015/lr15025/Intero.asp

⁵⁷ BCC Abruzzi e Molise (2021). *Cooperative di comunità: l'Abruzzo vuole ripartire dal basso*. BCC Abruzzi e Molise. <https://www.bccabruzzimolise.it/news/cooperative-di-comunita-l-abruzzo-vuole-ripartire-dal-basso/>

Each of these cooperatives has particular characteristics as regards, for example, degree of maturity, local roots, and relations with the public administration. Indeed, virtuous examples such as Aielli or Calascio show how the intrinsic poetry of places can be brought out. Instead, realities such as Campo di Giove or San Vincenzo Valle Roveto are examples of how models of proximity care can be built starting from the enhancement of sustainable food chains or through the construction of community emporiums.

BorghilIN network emerged to structure a working system that is able to bring together all the CBCs belonging to the network. The network's objective is to structure a development model for the most fragile local economies, capable of self-generating and bringing economic and social wellbeing to the territory by creating new job opportunities while enhancing the territory. CBCs work individually on local needs and synergistically with other cooperatives on larger and more structured projects coordinated by *Confcooperative Abruzzo*, the regional office of *Confcooperative* for Abruzzo.

10.3 Territorial resources

The Region offers a rich variety of resources that can be leveraged to foster local development and create opportunity of social inclusion:

- **Natural heritage:** Abruzzo's diverse landscape, including national parks and protected areas, offers potential for sustainable tourism and eco-friendly economic activities.
- **Cultural heritage:** rich historical and cultural traditions provide opportunities for cultural tourism and preservation of traditional crafts.
- **Agricultural heritage:** the region's reputation for high-quality, traditional agricultural products offers potential for niche market development and agritourism.

From many local stakeholders interviewed, the valorisation of these resources could foster local development while promoting social inclusion. A respondent underlined the willingness of many agricultural firms and cooperatives to participate in job placement projects for vulnerable people. At the same time, the respondent underlined the constraint to participation imposed by a structural lack of services in rural areas. In another interview, it emerges the role of valorisation of local resources as an opportunity for the youth to create entrepreneurial opportunities locally. Many actors that participate in the local development of rural areas are also providers of a variety of social services. This is the example of Community-based Cooperative L'Alveare, located in Tuffillo village. Born from a desire to revitalize the village of Tuffillo by attracting tourists, the Cargo Bike Project was established as an incentive for sustainable mobility. This initiative also ensured a home delivery service during the COVID-19 pandemic for individuals who could not leave their homes independently⁵⁸. Another example is the agritourism *Rurabilandia*, an agricultural enterprise located in Atri (Province of Teramo). *Rurabilandia* created an educational garden which employs PDWs.

⁵⁸ For more information, see: <https://www.lalvearecoop.it/#about-4>

11. Conclusion and potential focus of MAP

Abruzzo faces **significant challenges**, including rural depopulation, an ageing population, and economic disparities between coastal and inland areas. The region is prone to natural disasters, particularly earthquakes, which affect communities and infrastructure. Access to services in rural and mountainous areas is limited, affecting quality of life and economic opportunities. Additionally, balancing environmental preservation with economic needs remains a challenge.

However, Abruzzo's rich **natural and cultural heritage** presents significant opportunities for sustainable and cultural tourism and niche agricultural products. Universities and research centres in the region provide a foundation for innovation and human capital development. Strong community bonds and social cooperation offer resilience and potential for community-led initiatives. The growing social economy sector shows promise for innovative solutions to social and economic challenges, and the region's renewable energy potential and strategic location present opportunities for economic diversification.

Pilot areas for the MAP have been identified based on the prevalence of mountainous and rural regions, as well as the dissemination of CBCs. Thus, L'Aquila and Chieti Provinces have been selected.

Potential directions for the MAP in Abruzzo include focusing on integrated rural development, digital transformation, social innovation for service provision, climate resilience and sustainable energy, intergenerational knowledge transfer, collaborative governance, youth retention and attraction, and disaster resilience. These strategies could help diversify rural economies, improve digital infrastructure, deliver services innovatively, build climate resilience, preserve cultural heritage, foster collaboration, retain young people, and enhance disaster resilience.

Good practices involve considering the value of the local cooperative communities and the possibility of growing together.

The aim could be building community-owned enterprises that engage with Market tools in a vision of Common Value, small villages to be places where a good quality of life is possible and where the future can be concretely experienced through innovative projects.

The MAP has so far involved some of the CBCs on BorghiIN network, but the aim is to extend the MAP to a variety of stakeholders at different levels (local, regional, national).

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13. Partners

